

**STUDENTS' PERCEPTION AND INCREASING RATE OF CYBERCRIME
AMONG OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY UNDERGRADUATES**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work is owned and carried out by ROSANWO Obalaja Adedamola (SOC/2017/124) of the prestigious Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. It has not been lifted from another or submitted for any degree at any other university, within and/or outside the country.

This study is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) degree in Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

In loving memory of my late father, Mr. Michael Adenuga Rosanwo, I dedicate this work to honour his memory and the enduring impact of his inspiration and words of wisdom, which continue to uplift and guide me, especially during challenging times.

Also, I dedicate this study to my loving mother, Mrs. Abosede Rosanwo, for her unwavering support, encouragement, and countless sacrifices throughout this journey. Her love has been a constant source of strength. I pray the lord God Almighty continues to guide and keep her.

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ABSTRACT

Cybercrime, popularly known as yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria, is on the rise and requires urgent attention. Therefore, the study examined students' perceptions and the increasing rate of cybercrime among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduates. In a bid of achieving this, the study investigated the perception of undergraduate students as regards yahoo-yahoo, factors facilitating students' involvement, and social media content's influence on students' participation.

The Differential Association Theory and Routine Activity Theory was used to guide the study. It employed a mixed research approach with a convergent parallel research design. A total of 260 respondents were surveyed using questionnaires to gather quantitative data, and 13 respondents were interviewed for qualitative data. The sampling size was selected purposively and accidentally from Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students.

The research reveals that students of Obafemi Awolowo University are aware of yahoo-yahoo, an act which has dented the image of Nigeria and Nigerians globally. Factors contributing to the increase in cybercrime include financial gains, unemployment, influence from social media posts by "yahoo-boys," inadequate cybercrime legislation, and personal choices, as well as peer pressure, poverty, family background, societal acceptance of yahoo-yahoo, and poor parenting.

Based on the findings, the study proposes several measures to combat cybercrime among students. These include integrating cybersecurity courses into the curriculum, implementing stricter laws and punishments, promoting education and awareness programmes, establishing anonymous platforms for reporting cybercriminal activities, and providing scholarships and grants to help students focus on their studies.

Keywords: Cybercrime, Yahoo-Yahoo, Students Perception, Undergraduate, Yahoo-boys.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Cybercrime is an act of violating the law of the society through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) to either target networks, systems, data, websites and/or software applications, or aid criminal activities (Goodman and Brenner, 2002; Wall, 2007; Wilson, 2008; ITU, 2012; Maras, 2014; Maras 2016). These criminal activities vary from time to time and has assumed various forms over the years. It has become a devastating global concern, as it is prevalent in most societies of the world and affects businesses, corporations and individuals. Cybercrime started as breaking into computer programmes by hackers, for financial theft, and access to sensitive and classified information of businesses and government institutions. In 1834, the first cyberattack occurred in France, when a couple of robbers hacked the French Telegraph System and stole information from the stock market. In 1973, a local New York bank teller machine was used to embezzle over \$2 million. In 1988, a Cornell University graduate student developed the first worm which forces itself to install on computers and then count to know the number of computers connected to the internet, each installation infected computers and crashed them after a while. This worm damaged about 6,000 computers (around 10% of the whole internet as of the time) and repairing of the worm effects cost about \$100,000 and \$1 million (Climer, 2018). In all the above cases, we could see that there is no need for the physical presence of the perpetrators before they carry out their activities, hence, cyber criminals operate beyond the national geographic boundaries without necessarily being physically present at the crime scene. Cybercrime can be perpetrated by any one from anywhere in the world (Jack and Ene, 2016).

Cybercrime which is popularly known as *yahoo-yahoo* in the Nigeria society, is a kind of criminal act that takes place on the internet or computer. The name, yahoo-yahoo, came to bear in Nigeria following the attack on *Yahoo!*, an email service corporation which went under serious cyberattack between 2013 to 2016, having 3 billion of its users accounts hijacked, reducing its value to about \$350 million (Climer, 2018). In this vein, students and youth who were involved in activities linked to internet fraud, hacking, forgery and related crime were tagged as *yahoo boys* (simply because most perpetrators were male as of the time). As the utilization of the internet increasing daily in Nigeria, so also is cybercrime. This upsurge is associated with the increasing accessibility of broadband internet connections due to the arrival of mobile phone (in 1999 with roughly 350,000 users, which later increased to about 120million users by 2013) and decrease in data subscription fee (Folashade and Abimbola, 2013; Doppelmayr, 2013; Ojolo, 2018).

Peter Cassidy, who was the Secretary General of the Anti-Phishing Working Group, coined the term *cybercrime* to delineate computer programmes and coordinated, interlocking sets of programmes designed specifically to animate financial crime from other various forms of maleficent and pernicious software (Shehu, 2014). It is an act which involves the use of a computer, mobile phone or the internet as an instrument for illegal activities such as fraud, trafficking, child pornography, identity theft, social media hijack, hacking, fake job posting, sending of unsolicited emails, unusual calls and messages for auto teller machine (ATM) pin and bank details, bank verification number (BVN) scam, cyber stalking, virus attack, phishing, computer related forgery, unlawful access to a computer, cyber terrorism, cybersquatting, electronic card related fraud, purchase or sale of cards of another, credit card scam, among others. Cybercrime has continued to evolve overtime and this is because our society is evolving towards an information technology age, where communications and interactions occurs in the cyberspace.

This has made cybercrime a global phenomenon, which need to be explored. Unlike the traditional era, where criminals had to do their illegal activities physically, cybercrime, through the use of internet, has made it easy to steal, defraud and do various illegal activities remotely, at the comfort of the perpetrators zone.

The increasing rate of cybercrime is becoming alarming in Nigeria and other countries of the world (including the United States, Germany, Korea, India, among others). According to Ribadu (2007), Nigeria has been ranked first in the African society as the origin of malevolent cyber activities and target of cyberattacks, and this is widely spreading to other West African societies. The nature of cybercrime in Nigeria continues to evolve and change form of operation as new technologies emerges, especially with the emergence of social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, WhatsApp, and some online dating websites. Social media contents and posts of per-existing cybercriminal has been seen as a motivating drive for participation of new perpetrators (especially students) in various societies, as they also wish to live an extravagant and luxury lives. In Nigeria, cybercrime is more of individual focused than computer focused, and this is because perpetrators mostly use the computer and internet as an instrument to rip victims off their resources, defraud and harm them, rather than targeting the computer programme itself. Many individuals, specifically students, have espoused cybercrime as a means of survival and source of income at the expense of others (or victims) wellbeing- both physically and mentally. Statistics has showed that majority of perpetrators are undergraduate students, who falls between the age range of 18 to 45 (EFCC, 2022).

In light of the aforementioned, this study has provided insight into students' perception on cybercrime in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State Nigeria; the increasing rate of Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate involvement in cybercrime; how social media

contents of perpetrators influence students' participation in this illegal activity; and possible measures to be taken by government and its agencies in reducing cybercrime. In addition to this, it will provide an overview of factor influencing the increasing rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The problem addressed by this study is what undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University perceive cybercrime to be and those factors that facilitate the increasing rate of cybercrime among perpetrators, who are mostly young undergraduate students. As at September 2021, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) disclosed that, 80 percent of its 978 convictions were linked to cybercrime and its related activities (Guardian Nigeria, 2021). This shows that the increasing rate of cybercrime in Nigeria is becoming alarming and the one which needs quick intervention by the government and extensive research. Cybercrime hit thousands of businesses daily, as well as the country's economy, the government, individuals, investors, international communities and also, organizations such as banks. In 2018, commercial banks in Nigeria lost an accrue of ₦15 billion (\$39 million) to electronic fraud and cybercrime (Institute for Security Studies, 2020).

The prevalence of cybercrime cannot be overemphasized in Nigeria, especially amongst undergraduate students. Day in, day out, we experience increasingly alarming cases of cybercrimes, with each new case more and more outrageous than the other, and when this problem continues to persist it brings about; economic instability, discouragement of foreign investors in the country's economy, destroys the country reputation nationally and internationally, and also

make the business arena difficult for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) as well as start-ups. Hence, the need to fill these gaps in literature by suggesting feasible solutions to the menace of cybercrime and its related activities.

1.3 Research Questions

Furthermore, there's a need for a better understanding of the factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' participation in cybercrime and how social media content of cybercriminals influences students' participation. Also, this study has tried to educate the society about how students', who are seen as the main perpetrators, perceive cybercrime. More precisely, the following research questions will be addressed:

- i. What is students' perception of cybercrime?
- ii. What are the factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime?
- iii. How does social media (such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime?
- iv. What are the feasible solutions for minimizing the increasing rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students?

1.4 Research Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to examine cybercrime among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun state, Nigeria. The Specific objectives are to:

1. Understand students' perception as regards cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo);
2. Explore factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime;
3. Examine how social media (such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and WhatsApp) contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime;
4. Suggest measures that can be used in reducing cybercrime among University Undergraduates.

1.5 Significance of the Study

As at 2021, cybercrime had cost the world over \$6 trillion annually. It is the fastest growing crime in the Nigeria, United State of America and many other countries of the world and as it grows the perpetrations are increasing in form, cost and operations marking their terrifying effects on their victims (MailCleaner, 2018). Hence, there is a need for feasible measures in reducing cybercrime among students, which is one of the aims of this study.

In the same vein, the outcome of this study enlightens students, government and its agencies, and the society at large on some factors that predisposes students to participate in cybercrime in Nigeria and suggested possible measures that can be initiated in reducing the prevalence of cybercrime among university students and the entire population.

Although there have been many scholarly works on crime, but this study is peculiar in understanding the perception of Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students as regards cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) and how social media posts of predominant and/or pre-existing cybercriminals can influence students' involvement.

Finally, the results are beneficial for researchers in further generating more knowledge in the field of sociology, criminology and social research.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The centrepiece for this study was to understand the perception of undergraduate students as regards cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) and its related activities in Nigeria, specifically in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ile, Osun State. The study gathered information about yahoo-yahoo, its activities, factors responsible for its increasing rate, influence of social media content of pre-existing perpetrators on students and suggested possible measure for curbing and reducing its dominance in the society. Hence, the scope of the study was limited to undergraduate students across all faculties of Obafemi Awolowo University to represent the entire population, in order to avoid repetition of data.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for existing body of knowledge in research cannot be overemphasized, as there is a need for present studies to be informed by existing academic literature, especially on global matters such as Cybercrime. Cybercrime is a worrisome issue across all societies of the world, hence, the need for more social enquiries in addressing this melee and this can only be effectively done through the guardian and review of existing academic literatures such as scholarly publications (journals), newspapers articles, magazines, books, conference proceedings, government documents and other forms of academic papers related to the subject matter. This chapter would analytically review existing literatures on the subject matter, from the global viewpoint to the national context. The thematic style of literature was utilized, which comprises of two (2) subsections; the conceptual review, and the empirical review. The *conceptual review* is the subsection where the scholarly explanations of cybercrime and related activities are explicitly examined; and the *empirical review* is the subsection where empirical contributions of scholars in the field and articles would be evaluated and discussed.

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Definitions of Cybercrime

Cyber is a prefix used in describing any related activity involving computer and/or its networks (for example, the internet), it also connotes the relationship with information technology, while *Crime*

on the other hand can be defined as a violation of law, a behaviour not in conformity with the rules and norms of the society. Putting together, cyber and crime, cybercrime is a form of crime that occurs in the cyberspace (meaning, it happens in our world of modern technology and computer). Cybercrime delineates offences that have the potential of causing geopolitical and mental or psychological distress through the use of a computer and internet. The Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, defines cybercrime as a broad range of malevolent activities, which includes an unauthorized access to data, system hijack that disrupt or violate network integrity and availability, and copyright infringement.

The digital age has made our virtual identity an expedient component of our everyday life. As the computer has become central of commercial activities, entertainment and government, cybercrime has grown into importance. By the 21st century, hardly any hamlet would be found anywhere in the world that had not been affected by cybercrime of one form or the other (Dennis, 2019). It consists of illegal activities such as, internet fraud, identity theft, human trafficking, child pornography, intellectual property, violating privacy, among others.

Furthermore, the traditional form of criminalities does not involve the use of computers in its penetration and it requires the physical presence of the criminal, while the computer is the core of cybercrime. New technologies produce new folds of criminal opportunities and the major difference between the traditional criminal penetration and cybercrime is the fact that there is now the involvement and utilization of digital computers, but then, technology alone is not sufficient for distinguishing between the realms of criminal activity, as perpetrators do not necessarily need a computer to initiate their activities such as fraud, human trafficking, fake job posting, unusual calls and messages for auto teller machine (ATM) pin and bank details, purchase and/or sale of cards of another and others.

Cybercriminals may target an individual's private information, corporate database or government data for resale or personal theft. The necessity of connectivity to the internet has enabled an increase in the proportion and rate of cybercrime activities, as perpetrators no longer need to be physically present in the scene of the crime. The internet's speed, anonymity, and lack of traceable medium (through the use of VPN - virtual private network) make computer-based variations of financial related crimes - for example, internet fraud, money laundering, credit card scam - easier to execute (Brush & Cobb, 2021). These criminal activities can be carried out by individuals (or groups) with relatively low technical skills, or by highly organized global criminal groups that may include skilled programmers and other expertise.

2.1.2. Globalization and Emergence of Cybercrime

Cybercrime has been seen as one of the largest and globally most predominant kind of crime, and the reason is not far-fetched. The rapid development of high-level technological computers and internet has over the years, caused diverse problems which has made cybercrime assume an enormous dimensions and has made it a global phenomenon (Mohsin, 2020). Globalization has brought about various level of development in all societies which includes; widespread of innovation and high technology, invention of internet, ease of access to new cultures, lessen the costs for products, ease of access to new and upcoming talents, international recruitments, among others. Widespread innovation and high technology, and innovation of internet, as a product of globalization, has been useful in connecting the world together and made information very easy to access faster and easier. While some individuals enjoy the productive aspect of the internet and use it for their personal development, others engage it for their selfish, malevolent and fraudulent interest. The later made it possible for the emergence of cybercrime. Cybercrime has become a notable aspect of interest, as perpetrators, victims, and motives differ greatly in cybercriminal

activities (Ojolo, 2018). Cybercrime is not space-bound, because it is not restricted to any particular location nor any physical boundary. It has been seen as a modernized method of stealing, through the use of a computer. All cybercriminal activities happen within the cyber environment. From time immemorial, there have been various ways cybercriminals carry out their malicious attacks on government, organisations, and even individuals. Cybercrime have changed form and mode of operations over the years. The world had experienced various and some of the largest and most damaging cyber-attacks in history, below are some of the most well-known operations and attacks of cybercrime in record.

The 19th Centuries Cybercrime:

In the year 1834, *the Napoleon's semaphore telegraph* (that used mechanical arms on towers to relay coded signals all over France) was attacked by a couple of thieves which stole privileged information from the financial market. This makes for the first world cyberattack; ***The Switchboard Hack of 1870***, is one of the earliest cases of data intrusion. It happened when switchboard operators at the Bell Telephone Company intentionally redirected and disconnected telephone calls and used it to exploit private and sensitive information from users' line for personal gain (Squarespace, 2014); ***The Early Telephone Calls of 1878***, in New York, the Bell Telephone Company fired some staff for consistently and deliberately misdirecting users call (Acharjee, 2021).

20th Centuries Cybercrime:

Joybubbles of 1957, a blind 7-year-old boy, named Joe Engressia, was later tagged the US first phone hacker, hears a high-pitched whistle on a phone system and began to repeat alongside the

whistle at a frequency of 2600 hertz, which enables him to interact with the telephone system (Herjavec, 2021); ***Embezzlement of 1973***, Union Dime Savings Bank teller, *Roswell Steffen*, was used to embezzled over \$2million dollars using a computer program (Legal 60, 2021). Steffen was never apprehended before because he employed the most organized and inconspicuous instrument and computer to cover his illicit activity; ***Cybercrime Conviction of 1981***, Ian Murphy, who was popularly known as Captain Zap in phreaker's arena, was the 1st individual convicted of cybercrime after hijacking the AT&T database and resetting their billing timing system to invoice off-hours rates at peak-times; ***The Morris Worm of 1988***, Robert Morris is credited with inventing the first internet worm. When a fault in the worm's spreading mechanism causes computers to be infected and reinfected at a rate considerably faster than he expects, the potentially harmless exercise suddenly turned into a violent denial of service attack; ***NASA and Defence Department Hack of 1999***, Jonathan James, successfully infiltrate the US Department of Defence division computers and installed a backdoor on their servers, allowing him to intercept thousands of internal communications from numerous government agencies, including those revealing usernames and passwords for diverse military devices. He stole a couple of NASA application using the information he has with him. For the duration of three weeks, all systems were turned off.

The 21st Centuries Cybercrime:

Operation CyberSweep of 2003, as part of Operation CyberSweep, the US Justice Department announced over 70 indictments and 125 convictions for crimes such as; spamming, phishing, hacking and other related forms of internet fraud; ***TJX of 2006***, a group of cybercriminals hijacked about 45 million credit and debit card code from TJX, a Massachusetts-based retailer, and used a series of the stolen cards to make payment for goods on a Wal-Mart electronic shopping platform. Initial damage estimates were around \$25 million, while later sources put the entire cost of losses

at above \$250 million (Herjavec, 2021); *The Stuxnet Worm of 2010*, was the world's first digital weapon, a hostile computer virus, can hijack control systems used in supervising manufacturing sites. It is detected at Iranian nuclear power reactors, where it destroys about one-fifth of the country's enrichment centrifuges; *eBay, Cryptowall, and JPMorgan of 2014*, all of eBay's 145 million users' names, dates of birth, encrypted pins, and addresses have been exposed as a result of a cyberattack. In the same year, the forerunner to CryptoDefense – CryptoWall ransomware – is widely circulated and generates an estimated \$325 million in revenue. Also, hackers took over one of JPMorgan Chase's systems and stole data on millions of bank users, which was used in nearly \$100 million in fraud operations (Herjavec, 2021); *Prepaid Debit Cards of 2015*, by stealing a database of prepaid debit cards and then draining cash machines around the world, a global band of crooks stole the sum of \$45 million in a matter of hours; *Equifax and WannaCry of 2017*, was one of the main credit reporting agencies in the United States, has been hacked, with 143 million user accounts exposed. Dates of birth, addresses, driver's license numbers, and Social Security numbers are among the sensitive information that has been released; *Accenture Networks of 2021*, were infiltrated by the LockBit ransomware group, which encrypted files and demanded \$50 million in exchange for not having their encrypted files sold on the dark web.

In the above instances, we observe that in the 19th Centuries, cybercrime targeted more of physical properties, telephones and computer system of corporations and government, rather than the individuals. In the mid-20th Centuries, cybercrime focused its activities more on databases and attacks on corporate and government privacy. Around the 1970s, it has moved attention from the previous years to paying attention to financial related crimes and embezzlement of government and public funds. In the 1980s and 1990s, cybercrime had moved away from the realm of group operation to become an individual criminal activity – that is, a person can now on his/her own

carry out cybercrime activities without joining any gang – and was made possible because of the increase in the number of computer devices. In the 21st Centuries, attention is now fully based on financial crimes, advanced hacking and malware attacks.

According to Wall (2007), in his writings; *Cybercrime: The Transformation of Crime in the Information Age*, he suggested that: the *first generation of cybercrimes* and its related activities consists of traditional crimes where stand-alone computer systems are just a mere tool – they are classified as minute cybercrimes. From the 1970s onwards, *the second generation of cybercrimes* involve crimes assisted by indigenous or worldwide computer networks – these crimes can still be categorized as mostly traditional crimes, but with the invention of new breed of provincial issues and transnational opportunities. Furthermore, *the third generation of cybercrimes* accommodates pure crimes that are entirely facilitated by advanced technology – these represents a step-change in the growth and development of cybercrime.

2.1.3. Understanding Cybercrime in the Nigeria Context

The concept of cybercrime has been interpreted differently by different countries of the world and their activities has taken various forms overtime. In Nigeria, cybercrime is also referred to as *yahoo-yahoo*, and recently there have been an advanced version which is called *yahoo-plus* – the addition of supernatural and spiritual elements to compel victims (also called clients) to voluntarily adhere to all requested from them. Perpetrators of cybercrime (both *yahoo-yahoo* and *yahoo-plus*) in the Nigeria society are called *yahoo-boys*, because they both engage in similar activities, although with different methods.

Nigeria has Africa's largest economy and population, which contributes to the rapid growth and proliferation of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) and increase in the usage of the internet around the country. The internet, like other technological invention, has been exploited by both good and malevolent individuals. The use of the internet and computer devices to perpetrate crime is costing billions of dollars to the worldwide economy. Majority of Nigerians uses the internet for productive reasons, yet a certain proportion of the population uses it to engage in illicit activities such as internet fraud. *Yahoo-boys* in the country, specialize in internet fraud, primarily targeting international clients (Hamisu, Idris, Mansour, Olalere, 2021).

While most cybercrimes are carried out in order to generate profit for the cybercriminals, some cybercrimes are targeted against computers or devices directly to damage or disable them by releasing malwares or viruses into its systems. In Nigeria, for example, cybercrimes are mostly focused on generating profit for the perpetrators and not the other instance.

Cybercrime in Nigeria is perpetrated by *yahoo-boys*, as well as, interconnected networks of criminals, who are motivated by financial gains (Ogbonnaya, 2020), and their activities are becoming increasingly destructive with each passing day, wreaking havoc on the country's economy. Following the statistics released by the Financial Derivatives Company (FDC Ltd.) in 2020, the annual financial loss in Nigeria as a result of Cybercrime was approximately ₦250 billion (equivalent to \$649 million) in 2017, while in 2018 it had increased to ₦288 billion (equivalent to \$800 million). On March 10, 2018, a group of 'seven-man' hackers defrauded a bank in Lagos of about ₦900 million, which is equivalent to \$24,000 (EFCC, 2018). On September 2, 2020, EFCC officers arrested 13 individuals accused of being members of an Organized Cyber Criminal Syndicate Network (OCCSN), which defrauds unsuspecting victims of millions of Naira. Swift action is needed to be put in place by the government, in partnership with other sectors and

institutions, as it is proposed by the Consumer Awareness and Financial Enlightenment Initiative (CAFEi) that cybercrime is to cost Nigeria over \$6 trillion by 2030.

2.2. Empirical Review

In this subsection, we would examine previous empirical studies around the issue of cybercrime, in order to address a more specific issues in the course of this study.

2.2.1. Nature and Dynamics of Cybercrime in Nigeria

A rapid digitalization and technological advancement have taken place in countries of the world, including Nigeria, over the years. Although, this digitalization and technological advancement has brought about several advantages and improvement in way of live, it also came along with various upheavals and technological threats to the country. With the introduction of new and sophisticated technologies, the nature of cybercrime in Nigeria is forever and constantly changing forms and techniques. Some targets the computer system, as others targets individuals. In Nigeria, the majority of cybercrimes are tool cybercrimes (Kamini, 2010) – that is, cybercriminals in Nigeria primarily employ computer devices and the internet to dupe, deceive and hurt their victims (also called clients), rather than specifically targeting computer systems. Reason being that, the country has not developed to the level of adequately utilizing sophisticated technologies to attack computer systems directly.

Due to the internet freedom in Nigeria, the number of internet users has grown rapidly, as around 104 million people have access to the internet (Varrella, 2021), which has made more than 50 percent of its population liable to internet fraud and penetration. According to figures from Varrella

(2021), the number of online shoppers in Nigeria is over 76.7million. This has made the internet more attractive to organisations, businesses and entrepreneurs, hence, making them more liable to internet fraud, cyber hacking and other cybercrime related activities.

In Nigeria, cybercriminals activities vary and take different operating mode, for example, Dton – a 25-year-old male and career cybercriminal who uses the name *Bill Henry* to steal credit cards from his client and launches phishing and malware attacks on them, he had made over \$100,000 from his ‘profession’ within a short period of time. Also, the most recent and popular of all is the case of Ramon Olorunwa Abass. In June, 2020, during the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown, a Nigerian internet fraudster – popularly known as Ray Hushpuppi – was arrested on charges of conspiring to launder millions of US dollars to finance his flamboyant and lavish lifestyle, hacking and scamming. From the report gotten from the Dubai Police, Hushpuppi and his gang of 11 persons were apprehended and about US\$ 14million was seized, alongside 13 luxury cars which value \$6.8million; 47 smart phones and computer proof with over 100,000 fraud documents on approximately 2million victims.

2.2.2. Factors Facilitating Youth Participation in Cybercrime in Nigeria

A number of scholars and scholarly works have presented their personal perspectives on the various reasons and causes of cybercrime across countries, and also in the Nigeria settings. Below are the factors identified by Hassan (2012) as the causes of cybercrime:

Unemployment as explained by him, is one of the major factors encouraging cybercrime involvement in Nigeria. Most of the perpetrators of cybercrime are undergraduate students and young graduates, with a very large proportion of them without employment and have nothing to

keep them busy or even feed themselves. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Nigeria's youth unemployment rate has rose to 53.40 percent in the fourth quarter of 2020, up from 40.80 percent in the second quarter. The most amazing part of it is that, majority of them are tech savvy – skilful and knowledgeable in handling computer devices – hence, they feel it is an advantage for them to venture into cybercrime.

The Pursuit for Wealth, is also a factor that predisposes people to embracing cybercrime. Young people of this age are mostly self-centred and money-freak, hence, they decide to engage in cybercrime as they believe it is a channel for fast and quick money. They believe with cybercrime they can have enough to afford expensive lifestyles and meet up to standard.

Lack of Working Cybercrime Laws, which serves as an assurance that perpetrators can steal, hack, scam and do other cybercrime related activities without being caught. When there is lack of enforcement of cybercrime legislation and the government does not equip the agencies in-charge adequately, the interest and influence of perpetrators will begin to increase.

Insecurity of Personal Computers, can also make one susceptible to cybercrime. Most owners of computers do not adequately protect their computer devices from external attack and cyber penetration. When computer systems or devices do not have competent security, it makes them liable to cybercriminal activities, thereby opening the computer and information to theft.

In addition to the aforementioned, Okeshola and Adeta (2013) in their work on: *The Nature, Causes and Consequences of Cybercrime in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria*, pinpointed some motivating factors that can be responsible for the individual's participation in cybercrime, which are; money and financial gain, display of wealth by corrupt politicians and yahoo-boys, recognition and fame, low rate of arrest and conviction when caught, easy of perpetrating, intellectual pursuit,

parent(s) and guardian(s) lack of good moral upbringing of their child(ren), frustration, and dissatisfaction with personal earning.

Ojolo (2018) highlighted and explained two major categories that can promote youth's participation in yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria, which includes: peer group influence, poverty, social environment breeding yahoo in Nigeria, faceless nature of the internet and its impact on the growth of yahoo, ease of access to the internet, ignorance of the gravity of breaking internet law.

2.2.3. Classifications of Cybercrime

Over the years, the internet has grown at a breakneck pace, with the number of hosts connected to it expanding at an exponential rate every day. As the internet becomes more accessible and more services rely on it for day-to-day operations, the danger of the environment changes (Omodunbi, Odiase, Olaniyan & Esan, 2016). There have been diverse classifications of cybercrime and according to Brenner (cited in Maitanmi et al, 2013), this classification includes: *target cybercrime* (this cybercrime focuses more on the computer system as its target); *tool cybercrime* (this cybercrime focuses on the computer as a tool for penetration); *computer incidental* (in this category of cybercrime, the computer plays a minor part in the penetration).

In addition to the aforementioned, there are three (3) broad classifications of cybercrime:

Cybercrime against person and property: are cyberattacks or penetrations which are targeted at individuals, their privacy and personality. These are cybercrimes committed against individuals, includes: cyberstalking, cyberbullying, child pornography, spoofing, credit card fraud, libel or slander, e-mail phishing, unauthorized access and control of another's computer devices and others. Cybercrime against property includes: computer vandalism, disseminating Denial of

Service (DDoS) attacks, virus attacks, copyright infringement, Intellectual Property Right (IPR) violation, server hijack, unauthorized computer trespassing and possession of computerized information. If not well addressed by the government and other social institutions, can cause potential stifle in the development of individuals as well as leave irreversible stigma, injuries and can lead to suicide for some other victims.

Cybercrime against organisations: These are cybercrime activities targeted against firms, companies, and corporations. It includes industrial spying, network intrusions, web-jacking, malware dissemination, unauthorized computer entering, password sniffing, and forgery.

Cybercrime against government: It is any related cybercrime against government and its properties. This classification is often the least common cybercrime, but it is the most serious and the one which is not taken with levity, as it is seen as an act of war against the government of a state. These includes cyberterrorism, cyberwarfare, hijack for access to government confidential or classified information, government database hacking, attacking military websites, and propaganda distributions. These perpetrators are mostly viewed as enemy of the nation and terrorists because they viewed as a threat to international governments and its citizens.

2.2.4. Forms of Cybercrime

There have been many forms of cybercrime, here are some specific examples:

Internet fraud: is a breed of cybercrime fraud in which information is withheld or incorrect information is provided with the goal of defrauding victims of their belongings, heritage, or finances (Warf, 2018). According to definition giving by the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), it is the use of Internet services or software with internet connectivity to defraud and/or

exploit people. However, Internet fraud differs from theft in that the victim (client) willingly and knowingly give out their details, finances, or belongings to the perpetrator, as well as the fact that it involves perpetrators who are dispersed in location and time. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) Operatives of the Enugu Zonal Command, on the 16th of March 2022, apprehended 13 suspected internet fraudsters at the Nsukka and Emene area of Enugu State for internet fraud and items (such as phones, a Lexus car, and 5 laptops) were recovered. In addition, fraudulent activities can come in form of ponzi schemes such as Mavrodi Mundial Moneybox (MMM), Racksterli Investment, among others. On one hand, founders of this programs would launch a website where their clients could register, give opportunity for referrals and referral bonus, and give ridiculously high interest rate on investments. On the other hand, they do various forms of advertisement and even pay top celebrities to push their agenda.

Hacking: is the act of detecting and exploiting security flaws in a computer system, network or device in order to obtain access to personal or sensitive information of a person by using a password cracking technique or hacking tool (Williams, 2022). This is frequently carried out remotely by install a *backdoor*, and then the hacker can gain access to victims' activities. The most of hacking in Nigeria is that of wifi or social media hacking, whereby the perpetrator hijacks the victims' password and database for the purpose of either distributing pornography to friends and family, requesting for financial help from friends and family (in the victims' name), or selling the account out for monetary gains. This mostly occurs on social media such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, among others. On September 9, 2021, Justice Darius Khobo of the Kaduna State High Court sentenced David Kingsley to four months imprisonment for fraudulently hacking into unidentified Facebook accounts and committing fraud, with the offer of a fine of N100,000 (Vanguard, 2021).

Bank verification number scam: With the growing number of incidences of traditional security systems (password and PIN) being compromised, there has been a considerable demand for more secure access to sensitive and personal data in the banking sector, hence, the introduction of the Bank Verification Number (BVN) – a biometric identification system used by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to prevent or minimize unlawful banking activities in the country. However, there is a lot of risk attached to getting one’s BVN disclosed to the hands of cybercriminals (or yahoo-boys). For example, a victim received a mail from her bank with a link where she’s to input her BVN details for update and follow up of her account or she would face service suspension for not complying, because of the fear of losing her account and going to the bank for reactivation, she clicked on the link and inputted the details required. Some minutes, she received a debit alert of N1 million, before she could regain consciousness from the shock of the occurrence, many more debit alerts came in till her account was on zero balance. After several interrogations and questioning, she later opened up to have released some of her personal details after being sent the link to fill her BVN code.

Debit and Credit card scam: Debit card scam is when a criminal obtains access to one’s debit card number (and, in certain instances, one’s personal identification number code), with the aim of employing it in making illegal and unauthorized purchases or withdrawal of funds from one’s bank account (Fontinelle, Stapleton & Reeves, 2021). This form of cybercrime has been dominant in Nigeria since the introduction of the Cashless Nigeria Policy, which aimed at encouraging the use of electronic systems for all forms of financial or monetary transactions. Although, the policy has brought about various benefits such as the ease and security of transactions for a larger number of citizens, however, it has birthed an upsurge in e-banking and e-payment system fraud. This type of scam can be done in various ways. For example, perpetrators or yahoo-boys often make use of

a hidden video camera(s) to capture Debit card numbers – both the Permanent Account Number (PAN) and the Card Verification Value (CVV) – and the card pin, at Point of Sales (POS) stands, eatery, or at some unguarded Auto Teller Machine (ATM) spots. Perpetrators also uses method such as *ATM Skimming, Internet Order Fraud and others.*

Identity Theft and Identity Fraud: Although over the year, identity theft and identity fraud have been used interchangeably, they a quite different. When an individual’s personal information is stolen, this is referred to as *identity theft* and when the stolen information is used for fraud or other fraudulent related are activities, it is then called *identity fraud*. Identity theft occurs when cybercriminals gain forceful access to enough information about a person’s identification (such as their birth date, name, current or previous residence, and others), to commit fraudulent activities against the person, or in the person’s name (and this victim might be either dead or alive). Identity fraud, on the other hand, involves the use of stolen identity in criminal conduct in order to access products and services by deceit and under false pretence. Identity stolen can be used for the purpose of: opening bank accounts, obtaining credit cards and government benefits, getting loan from banks and corporative, ordering products and services, obtaining essential documents (for example, passports and driver’s license) in one’s name, as well as filing taxes and many others. Without the combination of the two, the activity of a cybercriminal is not complete, because they do not just steal to keep the information or stolen property in their possession, they are interested in stealing the information for fraudulent activities.

Other forms of Cybercrime include; Phishing *Intellectual property theft, Computer-related Forgery, Cyberstalking, Cyber terrorism, Cyber Plagiarism, among others.*

2.2.5. Socioeconomic Lifestyles of the Yahoo-Boys: A Study of Perceptions of University Students in Nigeria

Cybercrime is one of the most common types of crime done by Nigerian students at tertiary institutions (Aghatise, 2006; Adeniran, 2008; Tade & Aliyu, 2011; Aransiola & Asindemade, 2011). Although cybercrime is not unique to Nigeria, as it is a global situation, Nigerians' remarkable and widespread participation in it (particularly among university students), makes it a significant problem that requires swift attention. To Aghatise (2006), the fact that 80 percent of cybercriminals in Nigeria are students in various universities is so disheartening. As a matter of fact, many Nigerian university students have adopted internet fraud as a way of life; while some have grown extremely wealthy, others have been caught by the government agencies.

According to Adeniran (2008), young people, particularly undergraduates and those without employment, have accepted ICT to the point that they use the internet for the majority of the day and this is as a result of the advancement in technology. Students from educational institutions, as well as other young people in Nigeria who are active in cybercrime for the money they gain from their victims, have been prosecuted for their numerous illegal actions on the internet. Tertiary institution students, as well as other adolescents participating in cybercrime in Nigeria, have been widely acknowledged as leading a different lifestyle that sharply distinguishes them from other youths in the society (Adeniran, 2008; Tade & Aliyu, 2011; Aransiola & Asindemade, 2011).

According to Ojedokun & Eraye (2012), in their study on the *'Socioeconomic Lifestyles of the Yahoo-Boys in Nigeria'*, the majority of respondents regarded the financial strength of university students who are successful in their criminal activities as enormous, as they frequently make a lot of cash, by penetrating residents of developed countries with stable national economies and whose

currencies have far better foreign exchange values than that of the Nigerian currency. As a result, when perpetrators earn money through fake business proposals on the internet and other mode of scamming, their equivalency when converted to the local currency climbs dramatically, hence, making a number of them billionaires overnight. In addition, a percentage of respondents stated that students involved in cybercrime tend to spend their gains lavishly by hosting parties and clubbing, staying in hotels with girlfriends for weeks, purchasing luxury cars, expensive phones, and dwelling in a well-furnished apartment. According to Tade and Aliyu (2011), yahoo-boys in Nigeria have the status of big boys, and their flamboyant lifestyle is socially recognized among friends, family and university authorities.

2.2.6. Impact of Yahoo-Yahoo on the Nigerian Society

The rising rates of cybercrime in society have posed a serious danger to Nigeria's e-commerce expansion, resulting in a bad reputation that has unfairly denied some innocent Nigerians opportunities overseas (Abdurrahman & Jibril, 2017). The ramifications of cybercrime have a wide range of consequences for Nigeria's social and economic growth, posing issues for the government, organisations, individuals and the international community (Emmanuella, 2021).

The impact of cybercrime can be categorized into 3: Its impact on the government; organisations; and individuals (citizens and/or victims)

Effect on Government:

1. Cybercrime wreaks havoc on the country's image - the predominance of cybercrime has also tarnished Nigeria's image as one of the world's most corrupt countries, according to the Committee of Nations. Potential investors and visitors are both afraid as a result, and the government's taxes

and other income suffer as a result; 2. *Implications for the country's socioeconomic advancement* - cybercrime impedes the country's socioeconomic growth since it fosters distrust and lack of confidence in profitable activities, results in job losses and revenue loss, and encourages the denial of chances to innocent Nigerians overseas; 3. *Perceived loss of confidence in the nation's developmental progress* - foreign investments may find it difficult to flow into the economy as a result of the perceived loss of confidence (Umaru, 2020). When a country is tagged as a hotspot for cybercrime, potential investors are wary of investing in that country, hence, making the country an economic outcast.

Effect on Organisations:

1. *Financial Losses* - cyberattacks on businesses and organisations can harm an organisation's reputation and lead to a loss of consumers and revenue, as over 17,600 bank customers and depositors lost N1.9 billion in 2018 due to cyber fraud (Jackson & Robert, 2016; Ogbonnaya, 2020); 2. *Loss of Competitive Advantage* - when a hacker steals a company's confidential information and future business strategies, it puts them at a lesser advantage, especially when these are linked to their competitors; 3. *Increasing Costs and Productivity Losses* - cybercrime reduces an organisation's productivity and raises its operating costs, as large sums of money are spent on security software applications to reduce the rate of cyberattacks. This takes time and has a damaging impact on production of the organisation.

Effect on Individual:

1. *Reputational disadvantages* - because the country's image has been tarnished, citizens believe they are no longer safe, they seek safety and shelter wherever they can. Nigerians are treated with high degree level of suspicion and caution, even in the country they flee to for protection and refuge, because they are labelled as 419, yahoo-yahoo and scammers, who cannot be trusted; 2.

Psychological distress - for example, Cyber stalking instils fear in the victim's psyche by harassing and humiliating them, which necessitate an increase in security improvements in order to avoid additional penetration and threat.

2.2.7. Strategies Aimed at Reducing Yahoo-Yahoo in Nigeria

Despite the fact that cybercrime is a worldwide phenomenon, countries of the world are affected differently based on the laws in place to handle the problem and the effectiveness of their law enforcement and crime prevention organisations in combating the threat (Ogbonnaya, 2020). Efforts have been made by Nigerian governments and other stakeholders to stop the spread of the yahoo-yahoo operations in the country. As a result, the Nigerian government and financial institutions have formed partnerships to figure out strategies and remedies for dealing with the menace and decreasing its effect on Nigerian society. These can be accomplished in the following ways:

Public Awareness and Appropriate Enlightenment: To avoid cyberattacks, there is a requirement for adequate public knowledge of fraudsters' actions and operations, as well as users' education on the proper use of vital computer applications and internet security passwords. The Nigerian government should make efforts to organize regular programmes and workshops for secondary school graduates (both those awaiting admission into university and those unable to afford one), undergraduates, and recent graduates.

Enactment of a working Cybercrimes Law: The Cybercrimes Prohibition Act of 2015 "creates an effective, coherent, and comprehensive regulatory, legal, and institutional foundation for the proscription, prosecution, discovery, and punishment, prevention of cybercrime in Nigeria." The

Act must be reviewed on a regular interval in order for it to be successful in dealing with the present and dynamic nature of cybercrime and its related offenses.

Creation of the Cybercrime Advisory Council: A well-grounded Cybercrime Advisory Council has been established in order to minimize cybercrime to its bare minimum. A Cybercrime Advisory Council (referred to as “the Council” in the Act) was established to handle problems relevant to the prevention and fighting against cybercrime, cyber related offense, cyber terrorism, and the campaign for cybersecurity in Nigeria in order to coordinate the Cybercrime Act, 2015.

Collaboration between the government, and international and private organisations: The Nigerian government has inked a collaboration deal with Microsoft Nigeria, which would give a boost to the fight against computer and computer-related fraud and crime in the country. The Federal Government of Nigeria and Interpol reached a signed agreement on the Memorandum of Understanding to combat cybercrime, international crimes, and other related crimes. The MoU, will assist Nigerian police in opening and maintenance of better communication with other nations in the fight against all forms of cybercrime, and other transnational crimes.

Creation of Job Opportunities and Skill Acquisition Centres: Government should aim at generating several job possibilities for citizens, as well as encouraging small scale firms to function by lowering their tax rates, and providing grants and loans to help them maintain their businesses.

2.3. Summary and Gaps in Literature

Following prior scholarly works and studies on cybercrime and how it is perceived by different individuals, this chapter have been able to give a great insight on the global phenomenon known as cybercrime, its emergence from time immemorial till present day, and the general viewpoint of the phenomenon have been systematically reviewed and explained. **The Conceptual review** opened our understanding into various scholarly definitions of cybercrime, the growth and historical operations of cybercriminals over the years, how globalization and invention of internet, technological machines and computer devices have facilitated the advancement of cybercrime, and finally, understanding cybercrime in the Nigeria context. The study reviewed the definitions of cybercrime from several scholarly works all over the globe and also in Nigeria.

The Empirical review consist of literatures on nature and dynamics of cybercrime from the broader view to the Nigeria society, some factors facilitating youth participation in cybercrime in Nigeria and in the world at large, classifications and forms of cybercrime. Literatures have also been reviewed on the socioeconomic lifestyles of yahoo-boys, impact of yahoo-yahoo on the Nigerian society (which was divided into three; its effect on the government, organisations, and individuals), and strategies aimed at reducing yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria (such as job creation and establishment of skill acquisition centres, enactment of the cybercrime act, among others).

Although, several literatures have been reviewed in the course of the study, but then, scholar have left some important aspect untouched or unattended to, hence, the need to fill the gap in literature. Majority of prior literatures reviewed employs the qualitative research tradition while others employed the quantitative research tradition, but in this study, the combination of both research traditions would be utilized (which is known as the mixed method research tradition). The mixed

method research tradition enabled the study get more in-depth understanding into the perception of students on cybercrime and its increasing rate, and also help in addressing the setback of using a single research tradition because it involves integrating both the qualitative and quantitative research methods.

Also, this study filled the gap in space and time. Literature reviewed were done in different universities in Nigeria and in the world, but none have been done in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun state. In the same vein, majority of scholarly works on cybercrime among undergraduate students were long done, though they are still relevant.

Furthermore, several literatures have focused on the reason for the predominance of yahoo-yahoo among Nigerian youth, factors responsible for youths' involvement in yahoo-yahoo and factors influencing yahoo-boys flamboyant lifestyle on the social media, without paying attention to how the flamboyant lifestyles and social media post of yahoo-boys facilitates the engagement of students into yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria. Hence, this study examined how social media content of yahoo-boys influence students' participation in cybercrime.

Therefore, in a bid to fill these gaps in literature, this study explored the perception of undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University as regards cybercrime, factors responsible for the increasing rate of students of Obafemi Awolowo University involvement in cybercrime, and how social media contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime. Also, the study suggested measures in reducing cybercrime among undergraduate students in Nigeria and in the world at large.

The sample size for the study comprised 260 respondents for the quantitative data collection and 13 respondents for qualitative data collection, which made a total of 273 respondents in general.

This study employed the mixed method research philosophy, and primary sources of data collection was utilized. Also, the study equipped some well-grounded sociological theories in explaining cybercrime and why individuals engage in this malicious act.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In Sociological and Anthropological research, and in Social Sciences in general, theories have crucial roles to play and these roles cannot be overlooked or belittled, as it gives more explanations and insights to our study. This chapter is focused on reviewing existing theoretical ideas to serve as a roadmap for our study and placing it in the context of scholastic discussions. For this study, the Differential Association Theory and Routine Activity Theory was employed, following its aims and objectives which are: to understand students' perception as regards cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo); to explore factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime; to examine how social media contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime; and finally, to suggest measures that can be used in reducing cybercrime among University Undergraduates.

3.1. Differential Association Theory

The Differential Association Theory is a crime predictive model which was developed by the great American sociologist, Edwin H. Sunderland, in explaining why people commit criminal behaviours and delinquencies. According to Sunderland, individuals know nothing outside of what they have learnt from people around them, the association they keep, and those they have close relationship and contact with, be it their friends, family, clubs and others. He believed that we can only do what we have been taught and learnt from others in the process of interaction and

communication. That is, law breaking and deviant behaviours can only be possible when we have successfully learnt it from others. He continues to explain that, individuals did not just learn how to break or violate laws, they also learn the techniques, attitude needed, values, and reason why we must break these laws.

Differential Association Theory posits that all criminal behaviour is learnt, and the degree of contact a person has with criminals affects the learning process. That is, interaction or contact with criminals propel individuals to committing criminal behaviour because there is a possibility of learning such behaviour, and the more frequent the interaction and association with the criminals, the higher the chance of learning and adopting criminal acts and conducts.

3.1.1. Assumptions Of Differential Association Theory

Sunderland in his work, pinpointed some nine (9) basic assumptions and principles to further elucidate the Differential Association Theory, which are:

1. Criminal behaviours are learnt from others who are criminals.
2. Criminal behaviours are learnt in the process of interacting and communicating with criminals.
3. Learning processes usually takes place within a small and intimate group (and less from other means).
4. Criminal behaviour is not learnt in isolation, it also includes; 1.) learning of techniques used in committing crimes (which can be simple or tough, as the case may be); 2.) learning of specific motives, drives, attitudes, and rationalizations for justifying criminal acts.

5. Specific direction of motives and drives is learnt by defining the legal codes as favourable or unfavourable.
6. Individuals become deviants as a result of excess of definitions favourable to violation of law over definitions unfavourable to violation of the law.
7. Differential contacts or associations often vary based on frequency, duration, priority and intensity.
8. Learning process of criminal conducts by association with criminal and anti-criminal traits involves all of the mechanisms required in any other learning.
9. Despite the fact that criminal behaviours are an expression of general needs and values, these needs and values do not adequately account for it, as non-criminal behaviours can equally infer same values and needs (for example, sexual urges).

3.1.2. Application Of Differential Association Theory to Understanding Students' Perception as Regards Cybercrime and Its Increasing Rate

The differential association theory, is of the standpoint that individuals learn to participate in cybercrime based on their relationships with trusted peers which invariable exposes them to the criminal behaviour and attitudes, which necessitate them adopting the behaviour themselves. That is, cybercrime and its related activities have been learnt by a criminal in the course of their interaction with members of the group he/she keeps, and this group comprises of successful cybercriminals who shares all necessary information and give adequate training as to the way things are done in the profession. In addition to learning the criminal behaviour, the criminal also

learns the techniques needed for committing cybercrime, motives behind the act, the drives, rationale and attitudes needed to be successful in committing cybercrime. The techniques include, how to hack, tools needed to hack, how to convince clients to submit to their will, formats to deceive clients, among others. Individuals again learn the motives, drives and rationale behind criminal behaviours, one of which is the idea that the *whites* have stolen from their forefathers and it is time to make them pay for what they have done and get back, at least, part of the resources stolen.

In addition, the theory has made us understand that the frequency, duration, intensity and commitment of a member in the group will determine what will be learnt and how successful the individual will be. That is, the reason why cybercriminals do not joke with the association they belong and are so committed to the group is because their level of commitment determines if they would get help from their successors attention and get more tips as to how they can improve and become more successful in the profession. Also, they believe that when they are committed and situations beyond their control arises, they can get help from other members.

3.2. Routine Activity Theory

Routine Activity Theory is one of the major theories in sociology and criminology used in explaining why crime may occur. This theory was propounded by Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson in explaining why criminals make rational choices to engage in criminal activities. The focus of routine activity theory is to study crime as an event in relation to space and time, and emphasizing its ecological nature and implications, unlike other theories of criminality that focuses on factors such as psychological, biological and social, that motivates the criminal into engaging in criminal act. Routine Activity Theory tends to explain the reasons behind individuals' motivation to committing crime.

3.2.1. Assumptions of Routine Activity Theory

Routine activity theory believe that criminals or deviants make rational decisions before concluding to engage in criminal behaviours and that they are hedonistic. Felson and Cohen argued that, no one would commit crime unless there is the coalesce in time and space of three (3) important elements. These elements include: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and finally, lack of capable guardian.

Motivated Offender:

According to routine activity theory, a crime will only occur when there is someone who is motivated or attracted to a target or by a target. The evaluation of a scenario by the offender decides whether or not a crime will be committed. That is, only when a competent guardian is not present and the criminal believes the target is appropriate will a crime be committed.

Suitable Target:

To routine activity theory, just as there must be a motivated offender, there must also be a target which attract this offender. That is, there wouldn't be a crime if there's nothing to steal. Target of crime can be property, material, cash, electronics and even an individual, and this can be as a result of the victim's carelessness, location, flaunting of material wealth and others.

Lack of Capable Guardian:

The final phase of routine activity theory is the existence or non-existence of a capable guardian. According to routine activity theory, if we have a motivated offender and a suitable target without having a competent guardian, crime will still not occur. The violation of law can only be possible when the arrangements made by the government of a sovereign state, through its agencies (police, security guards, vigilante), is not capable or not available as at the time which the law was violated. Capable guardian can also include one's vigilant staff, friends, neighbours, co-workers or even CCTV camera and alarm.

Routine activity theory believes that if any of these three mentioned is missing, hence, crime will not occur. To them, no matter how suitable a target might be or no matter how motivated a person can be, without the third factor, crime haven't occurred or will not occur.

3.2.2. Application Of Routine Activity Theory to Understanding Students' Perception and The Increasing Rate of Cybercrime

In light of this theory, it is obvious that engaging in cybercrime takes a conscious effort by the cybercriminal as they think rationally before finalizing on engaging in the criminal acts, basically

because there is no one to checkmate them or stop them especially as it doesn't involve a physical location. Not only that, the cybercriminal also is motivated based on the calculative understanding that the benefit outweighs the cost.

The routine activity theory believe that the cyberspace has become more conducive for the convergence of motivated offenders and suitable targets because there's no competent guardianship. In Nigeria, for example, there is a high rate of poverty, high number of able individuals without jobs and people living below the poverty line, hence, this motivate some individuals into committing cybercrime as majority of them have some technical skills and are well vast in using computers. Majority of these individuals are undergraduates or youth who are without jobs but are seeking for one, and they see cybercrime as a veritable avenue to make money and live a better life, having some necessary skills to engage in it.

As the world we live in is more cyber-oriented and as more people are now encouraged to appear in the cyberspace, it makes individuals a suitable target and susceptible to cyberattack based on their conscious or unconscious actions. Conscious actions in the sense that, victims might be flaunting their wealth and material possessions while being ignorant that someone might be watching. This can also be out of there carelessness in displaying their vital personal information online. On the other hand, unconscious actions can be by mistakenly sharing some information that can be helpful to cybercriminals to initiate an attack or add more to the information they already have about their prospective victim.

Furthermore, the fact that there is no competent guardian have brought a lot of challenges and have opened more windows for cybercriminal acts, because it is a cyberspace where anyone comes in and goes out, it is difficult to have a capable guardian. Unlike the traditional crimes that involves physical objects, cash, and moveable property, in recent time, everything the criminals need now

are online so also is their targets, hence, the effectiveness of a capable guardian becomes an issue because they also do not have a physical location in the cyberspace. A capable guardian in the cyberspace can be an anti-virus, firewalls and other software and hardware settings. Also, the lack of competent guardian can also be in the aspect of not having a working cyber law, especially in a country like Nigeria, where cybercriminals believe even when they are been caught, they can find their way around things and escape the wrath of the law. By these, motivated offenders are more encouraged to go into cybercrime as they believe it pays and there no one to penalize them.

In submission, there are many motivated criminals online who can identify weak points and suitable targets through conversations in chat rooms, social media, or by testing the vulnerability of a system and breaking into its network which contain financial accounts or other unprotected confidential information. Cybercriminals and their victims interact via network devices and internet connections rather than meeting in real time location. This has served as an encouragement for cybercriminals (and upcoming cybercriminals); hence, the rate of cybercrime continues to increase.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter covers the methodology that was employed in the study, Students' Perception and Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduates, where the systematic process of collecting, analysing, and interpreting data to answer our research questions and objectives will be discussed. In this chapter, the study focused on the description of the research design that was utilized, the location of the study, the sample population and size, the sampling technique, sampling procedure, the method of data collection, the research instrument, the data collection procedure, the data analysis methods, the procedures for ensuring research ethics and rigor, and finally, the summary of the research methodology.

This section is a crucial part of our study since it enables readers to evaluate the calibre and validity of the study. Additionally, it aids researchers in ensuring that their study is grounded in scientific findings, and adequately and effectively responds to the research questions and objectives.

4.1. Research Design

This section is concerned about the overall plan and strategy that was used in conducting the research study. It focuses on methods and procedures that was used to collect and analyse data to address the research questions and objectives of the study. According to Leedy and Ormrod (2019), a research design is "a strategy or guide for carrying out research. In addition to outlining the steps for guaranteeing the authenticity and reliability of the data, it offers a framework for establishing the techniques and processes for data collection and analysis."

This study adopted the convergent parallel research design, which enable the study to be able to analyse and compare the quantitative and qualitative data collected in order to have a robust and well-informed outcome during interpretation. Furthermore, the mixed method research method was utilized in order to have an in-depth understanding on Students' Perception and Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduates, Ile-Ife, Osun State, as it combines the quantitative and qualitative research method. The research problem is better understood when quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques are combined than when one methodology is used exclusively. While quantitative approaches can provide numerical data that can be statistically evaluated, qualitative methods can offer a more in-depth knowledge of participants' viewpoints and experiences.

4.2. Location of the Study

The location of the study, Obafemi Awolowo University, is situated in the city of Ile-Ife, Osun State, the southwestern region of Nigeria, occupying a land area of about 11,961 hectares. Using the GPS coordinate, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife is located at 7°31'06"N 4°31'22"E. It is about 56km Northeast the ancient town of Ibadan in Oyo State. Obafemi Awolowo University, formerly known as the University of Ife, is a Nigerian institution of higher learning that is wholly owned and run by the federal government. To honour Chief Obafemi Awolowo, one of the university's founding fathers and a distinguished lawyer, patriot, and politician, the institution was renamed Obafemi Awolowo University in 1987.

According to OAU official website (2023), the university is organised into two (2) colleges, thirteen (13) faculties, one hundred and eighteen (118) departments, with approximately thirty-

two thousand, and four-eighty (32,480) students and about twelve thousand (12,000) staff. The citadel of learning offers a range of undergraduate and postgraduate courses.

Figure 4.2: Showing the Map of Obafemi Awolowo, Ile-Ife, Osun State.

(Source: Google Map of Obafemi Awolowo University, 2023)

4.3. Sample Population and Size

The sample population of a study is simply the subjects, collection of people or things chosen from a larger population to take part in a study of interest. Following the definition given by Rosnow and Rosenthal (2008), “the sample population is the portion of the wider population that is chosen to participate in a study and from which the researcher intends to draw his or her conclusions”. For this study, the sample population are the undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State. This is justifiable because, a large proportion of cybercrime perpetrators are undergraduates and young adults, according to EFCC (2022).

Sample size refers to the number of observations, subjects, or individuals selected from a larger population to participate in a scientific research study (Babbie, 2016). It is a crucial component of every research study, since it affects how precise and accurate the study's findings or outcome will be. A sample size that is too large could be time-consuming, expensive, and pointless whereas a sample size that is too small might not provide enough information to draw reliable conclusions. Therefore, the sample size employed for this study are the undergraduate students from all 13 faculties of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. A number of 13 respondents (1 each across all 13 faculties) for the in-depth interview, while 260 respondents (20 participants each across all 13 faculties in Obafemi Awolowo University) for the questionnaire administration, was employed to share their view on cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) for each representation. This reason for this is so that there will be equal representation, and because of the time and resources factor. Also, to avoid unnecessary repetitions.

4.4. Sampling Technique

Sampling technique is the procedure of choosing a group of people, subjects or objects to be included in a research study (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It is imperative to point out that the choice of sampling method depends on a number of variables, including the research topic, the target population, and the study's available resources.

Based on the sampling size and nature of the study, which employs the mixed method research, the non-probability sampling technique was utilized. The non-probability sampling technique is used in research where individuals, subjects or objects are chosen without regard to chance, random selection or probability. The likelihood of each member of the population being chosen for the study is uncertain and uneven, instead, the selection of the sample in a non-probability

sampling technique is based on personal preference of the researcher or availability of the participants. This form of sampling technique has been divided into several types, of which the purposive sampling technique and the accidental sampling technique was of interest to this study.

Selection using the purposive non-probability sampling technique is crucial, based on the fact that it allows for the selection of participants based on their knowledge, relevant idea, or experience about the research topic or question. Using the purposive sampling technique is necessary as the study seek to understand the perception of students of Obafemi Awolowo University as regards cybercrime and its related activities. It helps the researcher, based on his judgement, to select students who are well informed and knowledgeable about cybercrime and its related activities. On the other hand, using the accidental sampling technique is important based on the availability of the respondents.

4.5. Sampling Procedure

The sampling procedure is a critical step in every research study in ensuring the validity and reliability of research findings. It is the process and procedure taken in selecting a sample of individuals or units from a larger population. The study started with selecting participants from the population using the purposive non-probability sampling technique, then the accidental (especially in gathering the qualitative data). Based on their knowledge, experience, or competence, the technique entails choosing participants who are thought to be the most appropriate or relevant for the research.

4.6. Method of Data Collection

To better understand Students' Perception and Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduates, the study employed a mixed data collection method where

the quantitative and qualitative data collection method was used in complementing one another in order to get an in-depth information about the research study. The reason for this choice of data collection method is so that the gap in literature can be filled, and that the study can offer a well-informed data and result.

4.7. Research Instrument

In the bid to achieve the aims and objectives of the study, questionnaires were administered to the participants and interview sessions were setup. This is important because the study is using the mixed method research tradition, hence, a close-ended questionnaire was also employed in gathering quantitative data from the research participants, while a structured interview was used to help capture the qualitative data.

To elaborate further, the questionnaires was typically designed to gather information about the subject matter from the participants. It was administered via an online survey, followed a structured format and was closed-ended. On the other hand, the in-depth interview was conducted in a structured format, allowing the researcher to ask open-ended questions and follow-up questions based on the participant's responses in order to gain a deeper understanding of the participant's experiences and perspectives, and to explore the nuances and complexities of their views on the subject matter.

4.8. Data Collection Procedure

In collecting data from participants, a face-to-face interview session was arranged with 13 respondents across all 13 faculties, also, a close-ended questionnaire was administered to 260 undergraduate students across all 13 faculties of the institution. Respondents were purposively and accidentally selected at various faculties and lecture theatres, depending on their knowledge about

cybercrime and their availability. In addition, all instruments of data collection were carefully and properly managed, for the sake effective data analysis and interpretation of results.

4.9. Method of Data Analysis

The method of data analysis is the process of analysing and making sense data that has been gathered via research methods. Following the nature of mixed method research, the method of data analysis involves the integration of quantitative and qualitative data in a single study. The study will be using both the quantitative and qualitative methods of data analysis in interpreting the data collected and drawing conclusions.

In light of above, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) – a piece of software frequently used in business, social sciences, and other sectors where statistical data analysis is necessary – was employed for the analysis of the quantitative data, while the ATLAS software – a qualitative data analysis tool that enables researchers to compile, analyse, and display data in text, audio, and video forms – was used to analyse the qualitative data.

4.10. Ethical Consideration

It is crucial to take ethical considerations into account while conducting research on sensitive subjects, such as cybercrime, to make sure the study is carried out in a scientific and ethically sound way. The study will ensure all ethical standards and guidelines for everywhere scientific research are all adhere to.

To start with, all participants gave their consent before the research was conducted. This implies that participants had complete knowledge of the study's nature, goals, objectives and possible risks and benefits. They also had the choice of participating or not, that is, they might decide to opt in

or out of the study according to their will, especially at the point where they are beginning to get uncomfortable with either the researcher or the questions being asked. Also, the issue of confidentiality and privacy of information provided was protected, as a pseudo name was chosen by them.

Furthermore, as human being are products of culture, the study ensured that cultural norms and values of the participants was taken into consideration, and the research did not violate any of these norms and values. Additionally, the researcher ensured that any form of deception, misleading information or harm to the participants is avoided and shunned.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter of the study is where the analysis of the data gotten from the research field has been presented, interpreted, analysed and discussed. The data that is presented in this chapter was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and ATLAS.ti Software. Tables and charts were used for the data presentation, and interpretations of each table and chart then follows. The last section of this chapter focuses on the discussion of the findings from the 273 respondents employed in this study (where 260 participants for questionnaire and 13 participants for interview). The discussion of the findings of this study was done by giving lucid explanations of the findings as interpreted from the analysed data, and relating them with extant literature and theories.

Table 5.1. Socio-Demographic Background of Respondents

	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	122	46.9
	Male	138	53.1
	Total	260	100.0
Age	16 - 25	214	82.3
	26 – 35	44	16.9
	36 – 45	1	4
	46 – Above	1	4
	Total	260	100.0
Religion	Atheism	1	4
	Budism	1	4
	Christianity	201	77.3
	Muslim	51	19.6
	Traditional Worshippers	5	4
	None	1	1.9
Total	260	100.0	
Level	100L	56	21.5
	200L	40	15.4
	300L	50	19.2
	400L	80	30.8
	500L	34	13.1
	Total	260	100.0
Faculty	Administration	20	7.7
	Agriculture	20	7.7
	Arts	20	7.7
	Basic Medical Science	20	7.7
	Clinical Sciences	20	7.7
	Dentistry	20	7.7
	Education	20	7.7
	E.D.M	20	7.7
	Law	20	7.7
	Pharmacy	20	7.7
	Sciences	20	7.7
	Social Sciences	20	7.7
	Technology	20	7.7
	Total	260	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

In Table 5.1 above, the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents are presented. As shown in the table, 53.1% of respondents are male (which account for 138 of the sample size), while 46.9% of respondents are female (which account for 122 of the sample size). Also, as presented in the table, 82.3% of respondents are between the age range of 16 – 25, while those between the age range of 26 – 35 account for 16.9%, and finally, those between 36 – 45 and 46 – above account for 4% and 4% of the respondents, respectively. The reason for the discrepancies in the age of respondent is not far-fetched, and this because the study focuses its sample size among undergraduate students and most of them are within the age range of 16 – 35.

Furthermore, for equal representation, 20 respondents were selected across all faculties of Obafemi Awolowo University. Students at different levels were all represented, as 21.5% of respondents were 100level students, 15.4% were 200level, 19.2% were 300level, 30.8% were 400level, and 13.1% of the respondents were 500level students accounted for 56, 40, 50, 80 and 36, respectively. The reason for the variation in the levels is based on the nature of the sampling technique used for the study.

Table 5.1.1. Socio-Demographic Background of Respondents

No	Pseudo Name	Faculty	Gender
1	Tayo	Clinical Sciences	M
2	Seyi	Social Sciences	M
3	Annie	Administration	F
4	John	Arts	M
5	Segun	Dentistry	M
6	Zeed	Technology	M
7	Gesh	Sciences	M
8	Dan	Agriculture	M
9	Sam	Basic Medical Sciences	M
10	Sam	Pharmacy	M
11	Tobi	EDM	F
12	Susie	Law	F
13	Barnabas	Education	M

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

From Table 5.1.1 above, 13 respondents were interviewed from all faculties, for equal representation. During the interview, respondents chose a pseudo and they also gave their informed consent in order to carry on the interview and record the session. The interview respondents consist of 10 males and 3 females. The reason for the incongruences in the proportion of the gender is as a result of the sampling technique used for the study, which is the purposive and accidental sampling technique.

Table 5.2. Students' Perception of Cybercrime

Questions	Reponses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Are you aware of the phenomenon called cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) in Nigeria society?	No	1	.4
	Yes	259	99.6
Do you think cybercriminal activities are rampant among OAU students?	No	99	38.1
	Yes	161	61.9
Do you think cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) negatively affects the reputation of Nigeria?	No	12	4.8
	Yes	248	95.4
Do you believe that there are more male involved in cybercrime than female?	No	20	7.7
	Yes	240	92.3

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Following Table 5.2 above, 99.6% of respondents (which account for 259 of the sample size) revealed they are aware of the term cybercrime and what it entails, while only 0.4% of respondents (which account for 1 of the sample size) reveal that the term cybercrime is not familiar. This implies that cybercrime is a popular phenomenon and one which most undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University are knowledgeable about and aware of. The interviews offered some further insights into these results by giving some concrete overview of what cybercrime entails. Following the accounts by Seyi, Segun and Gesh:

...cybercrime is basically, in simple terms, a crime that are committed on the cyberspace, something like identity theft, illegal posting of another person's content, plagiarizing, posting contents that are not age appropriate, among many others. We also have the financial part of it through identity theft and taking money from someone without their knowledge. - in IDI_Seyi (Social Sciences).

...in Nigeria context, it is basically just people that dupe people, using internet mutually to get some money and what we call it in Nigeria is yahoo-yahoo and that's what some people do in our present country... - in IDI_Segun (Dentistry).

...yahoo-yahoo as the name is called in Nigeria, is just basically fraud ranging from different levels, you know, it comes by different names, "wire-wire", many different names. So, it's just basically fraud. Fraud that happens through the internet through the use of like social media in deceptive ways to takes people's money and stuff like that. - in IDI_Gesh (Sciences).

Furthermore, a per cent of 61.9% respondents (which account for 161 of the study sample size) hold the idea that cybercriminal activities are rampant among Obafemi Awolowo University students, while 38.1% of respondents (which account for 99 of the study sample size) of the study is of another opinion, as they believe that cybercriminal activities are not as rampant as people say it is. With this, we can deduce that cybercriminal activities are rampant among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students. Despite the fact that a higher percentage of respondents for the quantitative data revealed that cybercriminal activities are rampant among OAU students, some interviewees hold the idea that it is not. For example, following Annie's suggestion:

... OAU to me is not, we cannot compare the rate at which students venture into cybercrime like that of other schools. For example, Abeokuta, the rate at which people are involved in cybercrime there, it is not small. I feel like OAU is not up to them in that case. But then, student undergraduates are still involved in cybercrimes in OAU. - in IDI_Annie (Admin)

In testing whether or not yahoo-yahoo has negatively affected the reputation of Nigeria, 95.4% of respondents affirmed that cybercrime has negatively affected the reputation of Nigeria, while 4.8% of respondents affirmed that it does not affect. With this, it will be correct to say that yahoo-yahoo

has negatively affected the reputation of Nigeria. To further establish this, interviewees commented that:

... You see the case of Hushpuppi and the rest, being arrested and portraying Nigeria as being the country filled with a lot of cybercriminals, those kinds of things get to really affect the image of the country. - in IDI_Segun (Dentistry).

... this yahoo-yahoo within and outside the nation, people see us as one that they cannot deal with because they feel like if we should enter into business with these ones, we'll defraud them and then run away. And then this has painted a bad picture of us Nigerians. - in IDI_Annie (Admin).

92.3% of respondents are of the believe that there are more of male involvement in cybercrime compare to their female counterpart, while 7.7% of respondent negates this idea that perpetrators are more of male than female. Based on the high percentage of respondents who believe that yahoo-yahoo perpetrators are more of male than female, we can conclude that the male gender is the most dominant in this field. In addition, some interviewees also believe that yahoo-yahoo is rampant amongst the male than the female, for example, the report from by Sam and Tobi:

... I would say it's the males. I think there's so much pressure on the male. I mean, we live in a bias world. You find out that our culture has puts so much responsibility and demands on the male gender. - in IDI_Sam (Basic Med.)

... For gender, I think I know it's the male. The reason why I said I know it's male is because looking at the news, social media, television, we see that they parade male most, most times. It's only few cases where we've seen female. - in IDI_Tobi (EDM)

During the interview session, interviewees raised issues around the correlation between yahoo-yahoo and age, as it is believed that cybercriminal activities are seen as rampant among people of age 15 to 40years. Take for example report from John and Dan:

*... Let me say I've not caught him right-handed, but I know he's doing it. The boy should not be more than 14 to 15 years old. Also, based on the kind of cybercrime that we are experiencing in Nigeria, majorly the poor are the ones that do it more. - in **IDI_John (Arts)***

*...I would say probably, I'll start from 16, as long as you have started using phone. When they started using mobile phone. The age of 16, I can't stop at any other higher age, probably 40 years, Maybe 40. - in **IDI_Dan (Agric.)***

Also, 76.9% of interviewees believed that those in the lower social class tend to engage more in cybercriminal activities compared to those in the upper social class, while 23.1% of interviewees believed engagement in cybercrime is not social status based, as perpetrators can be from both classes. This can be more explained following the account from Annie and Barnabas:

*...those that are more into cybercrime are of the lower class, because these ones most times they want to feel among or most times they're living from hand to mouth. - in **IDI_Annie (Admin.)***

*...it's the poor people that are mostly involved in cybercrime and their target is the rich people. - in **IDI_Barnabas (Edu.)***

Figure 5.1. Factors Responsible for the Increasing Rate of Students’ Involvement in Cybercrime

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

i. Financial Reasons:

From Figure 5.1 above, 220 of the study respondents perceived financial reasons as a factor responsible for students’ participation in cybercrime. On the other hand, 21 of the sample size disagree that financial gain is not a reason for the increasing rate of students’ involvement in cybercrime. 19 of the respondents are of a neutral opinion. With this, it is clear that financial reasons can be a factor that influences student into engaging in cybercrime. As some interviewees stated:

...we have the rate at which things are, the economy is not smiling too, so things are hard. People just even want to survive. So, people just want to eat. Some people want to pay school fees. So, that is part of it also... - in IDI_Annie (Admin).

...economic situation of the country, yes, there are no jobs. To even do legal jobs is not that easy, and you will not even get what you deserve in term of payment. So, when they see another means to just get a lot, they will go for it. - in IDI_John (Arts).

ii. Lack of Job Opportunities

Following the data gotten from respondents, 211 of the study respondents perceived the lack of job opportunities as one of the factors responsible for the increasing rate of student's involvement in cybercrime, while 23 of the study sample size believe that the lack of job opportunities does not correlate to the increasing rate of student's involvement in cybercrime. However, 26 respondents took a neutral standpoint. In justifying the lack of job opportunities as a factor responsible for students' involvement in cybercrime, Annie and John stated that:

... In fact, there are no opportunities for the undergraduates to work, not all student get money from home. Some people tend to send themselves to school. So, when they see that these things weigh them down, these expenses weigh them down, they have to get material, they have to feed. Transport fair is increasing as we have now, transport fair has doubled. These people have to look for a way to survive. So, there should be job opportunities. - in IDI_Annie (Admin).

...there are no jobs. To even do legal jobs is not that easy, and you will not even get what you deserve in term of payment. So, when they see another means to just get a lot, they will go for it. - in IDI_John (Arts).

iii. Peer Pressure

As shown in Figure 5.3, 220 respondents agree to peer pressure as one of the factors responsible for the increase in students' involvement in cybercrime, while 10 respondents disagree to the fact

that peer pressure is a factor responsible for the increasing rate of students' participation in yahoo-yahoo. Also, 30 respondents held a neutral standpoint as regards this issue. In supporting the claim that peer pressure is a key factor, interviewees commented that:

...peer pressure. If I, told that for instance after the covid students are coming in with exotic cars, exotic car, and people are driving no longer on the streets, people are coming with iPhones lit, iPhones lit gadgets. And of course, that's, that's some pressure. That's some pressure whether we like it or not especially for the young mind. Uh, so I think that peer pressure too is also another major factor. - in IDI_Sam (Basic Med.)

... another thing also is peer pressure. They are seeing a lot of people do it that I feel like they want to be among and they also do it also. - in IDI_Barnabas (Edu)

iv. Influence from Social Media Post of Yahoo-boys

The Figure 5.3 above, shows that 197 of respondents agree to the fact that the influence from the social media posts of yahoo-boys is strongly related to the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime, 37 respondents disagree with the opinion, while 26 respondents held a neutral view of the issue. With this, we can establish that social media posts of cybercriminals are motivating factor for students' participation in cybercrime. As some interviewees stated:

...Men are product of influence. If you stay on social media long enough, you come under that influence. So, if you are still watching those things long enough on social media, it can weary your mind, and before you know it, you're tempted to go in that line. - in IDI_Sam (Basic Med.)

...on social media, there's a way that social media tend to glamorize success even when it's not real. It paints balloon success and people are being oppressed. - in IDI_Sam (Pharmacy)

v. Personal Decision

Another detail shown in the table is that of the individual personal decision as a factor responsible for students' involvement in cybercrime, 234 respondents agree that the individual personal decision usually drive them into the involvement I cybercrime, 30 respondents posited that personal decision is not a factor which we can bank on, while 33 of the respondents tend to stay neutral. The interview with some participants has revealed that this is so and it as a result of greed. The personal decision to participate in this unlawful act is based on the innate greed in the cybercriminal. To compliment this, Seyi and Tobi stated that:

...I would like to start from the personal, how the society may have failed the person. So, I think as a person despite your problem, or what you may be going through, I think what drives people mostly is greed. Because most of these guys who tell you, their parents are poor, they can't afford school fees, and they take care of myself. Then they start, but after making some money, instead to stop, because of their greed, they continue this illegal act. - in IDI_Seyi (Social Sciences).

...if you're not contented with what you have and you are covetous you are greedy; you always want to have more. And since you don't have a good source of income, you don't have a business, you always do anything that will make you have money. - in IDI_Tobi (EDM).

In the course of the interaction during the interview session, the interviewees, give some cogent points and factors responsible for the increase rate of cybercrime among. For example, poverty, poor parenting, family background, fear of the future, economic instability, societal acceptance, lack of satisfaction with their course of study, and many other. As interviewees stated:

...fear of the future. They're afraid what will happen in the future. So, they want to be in it quickly, let's make this money. And many of them end up losing their lives. They end up not fulfilling what they're meant to do. - in IDI_Barnabas (Edu)

*...poor parenting from home, because the home as well has a lot to do as has a very strong influence on the child and even when he or she gets to school. - in **IDI_John (Arts)***

*...our culture now celebrates them; people don't care how you get the money provided you can spend it. - in **IDI_Sam (Pharmacy)***

*...I feel family background is a factor. Peer pressure also from friends and social influences. - in **IDI_Susie (Law)***

Table 5.3. How do Social Media (such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) Contents of Cybercriminals Influence Students' Participation in Cybercrime?

		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Have you ever come across any yahoo-boys flamboyant post while surfing the above social media platform?	No	36	13.8
	Yes	224	86.2
Has the extravagant lifestyle of Yahoo boys prompted you to explore alternative means of earning income?	No	177	68.1
	Yes	83	31.9
Do you believe that social media contents of cybercriminals can influence students' participation in cybercrime?	No	22	8.5
	Yes	238	91.5
Do you think social media plays a role in promoting the activities of yahoo-yahoo in the cyberspace?	No	30	11.5
	Yes	230	88.5
Have you ever fallen victim to cybercrime, or has anyone in your family?	No	164	63.1
	Yes	96	36.9
If yes, do you think social media played a role in the victimization?	No	139	53.5
	Yes	121	46.5
Do you think social media platforms and the government can work together to control the flaunting of wealth by Yahoo boys on social media?	No	40	15.4
	Yes	220	84.6

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The data (Table 5.3) provides insights into the influence of social media on cybercrime. When asked if participants have come across any flamboyant posts by Yahoo boys on social media, 36

respondents (13.8%) answered "No," while the majority of 224 respondents (86.2%) answered "Yes." This suggests that a significant portion of the sample has encountered such posts. A similar pattern emerges when participants were asked if social media plays a role in promoting the activities of Yahoo boys in the cyberspace. 230 respondents (88.5%) answered "Yes," while only 30 respondents (11.5%) answered "No." This indicates that the majority of respondents perceive social media as playing a role in promoting Yahoo-Yahoo activities.

*...everybody wants to look cool. Everybody wants to look like a big boy. Everyone wants to make it. So, if the image that keeps flashing on my phone screen 24/7, is that of a yahoo-boy in Porsche, I think it won't be bad if I ask him how he's doing it. - in **IDI_Sam (Pharmacy)***

*...an average male who uses those social media platforms, now they go online, they see people living a very flashy lifestyle and they feel the quickest way to make money is by going into cybercrime and all of that. - in **IDI_Susie (Law)***

Out of the respondents who have seen Yahoo-Boy flamboyant posts, 177 (68.1%) stated that it has prompted them to explore alternative means of earning income. Conversely, 83 respondents (31.9%) reported that it has not influenced their income sources. This indicates that the extravagant lifestyle displayed by Yahoo boys on social media does have an impact on individuals' pursuit of alternative income.

When asked whether social media content of cybercriminals can influence students' participation in cybercrime, 238 respondents (91.5%) answered "Yes," while only 22 respondents (8.5%) answered "No." This suggests that there is a widespread belief that social media content can indeed influence students to engage in cybercrime activities. Similarly, many interviewees mentioned that individuals are influenced by the flamboyant display of wealth by cybercriminals on platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter.

*...Social media, like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter, what they see there and feed their minds on it, then fill their possibility to turn to cybercrime- in **IDI_Seyi (Social Sciences)***

*...I think the flamboyant display of wealth of yahoo-boys influence students because it's just like, peer pressure. When you see someone you know or guys that are not even so close to you, displaying their wealth online, or maybe you even hear about that, then it depends on the person's personality not to feel intimidated. - in **IDI_Tayo (Clinical Sciences)***

Of the respondents, 164 (63.1%) reported being victims of cybercrime or having a family member who has been victimized, while 96 respondents (36.9%) answered "No." Among those who have experienced victimization, a significant number stated that social media played an important role, while others stated that it did not. This suggests that there is an increase of cybercrime, and social media plays an important role in these victimizations, in some cases. Interview data reveal that all of the respondent has either been a victim or have knowledge of someone who has fall victim of cybercrime:

*...there was this day someone just came into my DM, I joined the group, then they said we are doing contact gain with them, from there I met this guy, then I started viewing his status. Then he posted something you send me 2,000naira, I send you 4,000naira. I fell for it and I think I lost about 5,000naira there. - in **IDI_Sam (Pharmacy)***

*...personally, I've not been a victim nor any of my immediate family, but then, a family friend fell victim of an investment which was legit until it wasn't. I think they lost about 24million naira into that company. - in **IDI_Seyi (Social Science)***

When asked about the potential collaboration between social media platforms and the government to control the flaunting of wealth by Yahoo boys, 220 respondents (84.6%) answered "Yes," while 40 respondents (15.4%) answered "No." This indicates that a significant majority believe in the potential effectiveness of such cooperation. Although, some interviewees believed there are limited things the cooperation between these two parties can do because of not all those posting

flamboyantly are cybercriminals and also because of the data privacy. However, a significant number of interviewees believed this cooperation will work. Some interviewees stated that:

*...once there's a lot more security on these social media platforms, there will be a reduction in cybercrimes. Probably through the process of verification in opening all the social media platforms and facial recognition, probably and identity card to open the account so that they are afraid of committing any cybercrime. - in **IDI_Zeed (Tech.)***

*...I think they can regulate it by what they post. Once they start posting flashy pictures, they can like give a warning or like regulation that, due to this post we'll have to take it down, so that in case such person wants to post such thing again next time... - in **IDI_Susie (Law)***

Figure 5.2. Feasible Solutions for Minimizing the Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Undergraduate Students

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

i. Stricter Laws and Punishment

The multiple bar chart analysis yielded several solutions, indicating the prevailing consensus among respondents regarding effective measures to mitigate cybercrime among students. The data demonstrates that a majority of participants (195) strongly support the implementation of strict laws and stringent penalties as a deterrent against cybercriminal activities, as it has proven to be instrumental in curbing the escalating rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students. Conversely, a minority of respondents (39) expressed disagreement, while a smaller subset (26) remained neutral regarding the feasibility of such legislative measures. Insight from the interview

data reveal that universities and the government need to monitor students' activities, especially their digital devices, to detect, prevent and minimize cybercrime.

...the university can also play very key in putting a stop or maybe reducing cybercrime on campus. I think one of the majors they can put in place is to, I invested to. Where the school authority can maybe set up a policy to check the devices of students. - in IDI_John (Arts)

Utilizing detectives or undercover agents to investigate cybercrime incidents, including placing them in student hostels, to deter potential offenders. Most interviewees suggested that the government should increase the punishment for cybercrime and enforce it promptly to create a deterrent effect. While most interviewee opt for stiffer punishment, some interviewee suggested the need to offering vocational training programs that equip individuals with relevant skills and help them turn away from cybercrime.

...there's also the problem of prisons being overfilled and recidivism. Most of these guys, that commit cybercrime and end up in prison meet with hardened criminals and it would make them worse. So, I think the government can create a program for people that are into cybercrime to find a way to turn their skill into something that can be meaningful for the society. - in IDI_Seyi (Social Sciences)

ii. Education and Awareness Programme

In terms of education and awareness programs, a negligible number of participants (20) expressed disagreement regarding the significance of these initiatives in reducing the prevalence of cybercrime among undergraduate students, whereas a modest number (29) remained neutral about the feasibility of implementing such educational programs. The majority of respondents (211) indicated their agreement with the effectiveness of education and awareness programs in addressing cybercrime. Similarly, from the interview data, creating counselling services and

awareness programs to address the influence of peer pressure and discourage students from participating in cybercrime.

*...Some people they just get schooling and that is all, some people don't even get anything. They just tend to fend for themselves in school. So, if there can be opportunities for students, scholarship grants and all, if you want to write projects, there should be a support from the government for student. I think that would help. - in **IDI_Annie (Admin)**.*

Education was seen as a crucial approach to tackle cybercrime. Interviewees suggested focusing on technology and legitimate ways of making money, they also urge government to encourage youth to pursuit for education, by providing scholarships and grants, and reward students for their efforts.

iii. Cybersecurity Course

Regarding the integration of cybersecurity courses into the school curriculum, a substantial number of participants (220) expressed agreement, with a smaller proportion (28) adopting a neutral stance, and a minority (12) indicating disagreement. In addition, interview data reveal that the integration financial literacy courses in the educational curriculum to teach students about handling money, entrepreneurship, and making legitimate income can minimize and prevent cybercrime.

*...One way to address this is, applied knowledge. They should ensure that it is whatever you are teaching should also teach people on finances. Teach people how to make money legally like kids in, because many of these people, they don't want to actually do it. - in **IDI_Barnabas (Edu)***

iv. Report Cybercrime Activities

With respect to the creation of reporting mechanisms to combat cybercriminal activities, a significant number of respondents (182) agreed with this proposal, while a considerable number (50) remained neutral, and a minority (28) expressed disagreement. Interviewees emphasized the need for universities to implement control measures, such as registering students' cars before entering the campus, to enhance security and prevent unauthorized access.

*...I think probably putting in place detectives. People that monitor or just kind of watch, they might even put them in hostel as a student. Just put them at that so they'll get to be able to investigate and get... the more people know people are getting caught easily, it will be hard for people to do it on campus. - in **IDI_Dan (Agric)***

v. Role of Government

Regarding the role of government, most participants (138) expressed disagreement on the idea that government is doing enough to minimize the cybercrime among students. with a smaller proportion (62) adopting a neutral stance, and a minority (60) indicating agreement. This implies that, the government have not been really doing their best in minimizing the rate of cybercrime among students. The interviewees suggest measure that the government can utilize to reduce cybercrime among students, as Tayo stated:

*...the government can create enough employment opportunities and build the economy. Government should also try to encourage the youth through the educational system, like encourage them to be more involved in education, sports and other areas. With these, I feel the rate of cybercrime will reduce. - in **IDI_Tayo (Clinical Science)**.*

Discussion and Findings

The aim of this study is to understand students' perception and the increasing rate of cybercrime among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students. In achieving this aim, some set of objectives has been designed, which are: to understand students' perception as regards cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo); to explore factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime; to examine how social media (such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and WhatsApp) contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime; and to suggest measures that can be used in reducing cybercrime among University Undergraduates.

To successfully address these objectives, the mixed method research design was used, where 260 undergraduate students across all faculties were employed for the gathering of quantitative data using a closed-ended questionnaire, and 13 undergraduate students across all faculties were interviewed using a structured in-depth interview. For the quantitative data collection, both genders were represented in the study with 46.9% of Female and 53.1% of Male, all which are from different religious background, as some were practicing Atheism (4%), Buddhism (4%), Christianity (77.3%), Islam (19.6%), Traditional Worshipping (4%), and a respondent does not belong to any religious background (1.9%); while for the qualitative data collection, both genders were also represented as we have 10 males and 3 females, one was picked from each faculty. All respondents are of different age group which ranges between 16 – 45, from various level of the university (100L to 400L).

The essence of our study has been effectively addressed through the data collected, which was organized into four themes. The first theme which revolve around students' perception of cybercrime has been able to give us an elicit explanation of students' awareness of cybercrime and

it was established that undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University are well informed about cybercrime and what it entails; the predominance of yahoo-yahoo among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students is considered to be increasing, as yahoo-yahoo is seen as rampant among undergraduate students; yahoo-yahoo has negatively affected the reputation of Nigeria and it was established that cybercrime has dented the image of Nigeria globally, as Nigerians are viewed generally as scammers; finally for this theme, the category of people involved in this act is considered as more of the poor than the rich, and more of male than female counterparts. Also, based on the findings of this theme, it was suggested that perpetrators' age range spans from 15 – 40 years old.

The second theme of our study focuses on the factors contributing to the increasing rate of involvement of students in cybercrime. A thorough analysis was conducted to examine the key factors responsible for students' engagement in cybercrime. Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that several factors play a significant role in this phenomenon. These factors include financial gains, limited job opportunities, greed, influence from social media posts by "yahoo-boys," inadequate cybercrime legislation, and personal choices, as well as peer pressure, poverty, easy access to online information, societal acceptance, poor parenting, family background, and the absence of effective cybercrime laws were identified as contributors to the increasing rate of cybercrime among students. These findings align with Hassan's (2012) research, which highlighted unemployment, the pursuit of wealth, and the lack of effective cybercrime legislation as contributing factors to the growth of cybercrime. Furthermore, the study concurs with Ojolo's (2018) work, which emphasized the influence of peer groups, poverty, the socio-cultural environment fostering cybercrime in Nigeria, the anonymous nature of the internet facilitating

cybercrime, easy internet accessibility, and ignorance regarding the severity of internet law violations as factors driving the increasing rate of cybercrime.

The third theme of our study focuses on the impact of social media content of "yahoo-boys" on students' participation in the illegal conduct. It also addresses the role that the government and social media platforms can play in regulating the extravagant display of wealth by "yahoo-boys" on social media. The findings of this study suggest that social media content associated with "yahoo-boys" has a significant influence on student participation, and this influence is likely to persist unless appropriate measures are implemented. A staggering 91.5% of respondents believe that social media content created by cybercriminals can act as a catalyst for students' involvement in such activities. Additionally, a notable number of respondents who have either personally fallen victim to cybercrime or have had acquaintances affected by it, indicated that social media platforms played a role in their victimization. Therefore, it is crucial to establish effective measures to regulate the portrayal of wealth by "yahoo-boys" on social media platforms in order to mitigate the influence it has on students and prevent further harm.

Lastly, the fourth theme of our study focuses on providing solutions to reduce the growing prevalence of cybercrime among undergraduate students. It also explores the impact of the increasing rate of "yahoo-yahoo" on Nigeria's global perception and suggests measures that university authorities can adopt to effectively address cybercrime among their students. The study has successfully put forward practical solutions to minimize the rising occurrence of cybercrime among undergraduate students. These solutions encompass various approaches, including the integration of a cybersecurity course into the curriculum, the implementation of stricter laws and penalties, educational and awareness programs, the establishment of anonymous reporting platforms, the provision of scholarships and grants, the enforcement of university regulations, and

the creation of job opportunities. Some of these measures are in alignment with that which was proposed by Ogbonnaya (2020), for example, creation of job opportunities, enactment of a working cybercrime law, and public awareness and enlightenment. By adopting these feasible measures, we can work towards mitigating the prevalence of cybercrime among undergraduate students while also improving Nigeria's global image.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter is dedicated to the summary of the entire study from the beginning of the chapter to the fifth chapter of the study. It would then present the conclusion of the study in relation to the findings gathered from the respondents of the research. Finally, the section gives recommendations as gotten from respondents for combating cybercrime among students.

6.1. Summary of the Study

This study aimed at understanding students' perception and the increasing rate of cybercrime among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students. In a bid to achieving this, the study was sectioned into six chapters, where each part addressed different issues around the topic. These parts include: chapter 1 (introduction), chapter 2 (literature review), chapter 3 (theoretical framework), chapter 4 (methodology), chapter 5 (data presentation, analysis and interpretation), and finally chapter 6 (summary, conclusion and recommendation).

The first chapter encapsulates the background of the study, where the researcher explains the concept of cybercrime and draw attention to rate at which cybercrime is increasing among students, the damage it has done for the world and how social media have aided this increase. The chapter further encompass statement of the problems, where the research opens the readers' eyes to the need for more research around cybercrime as it has eaten deep into the fabric of many societies and the need to proffer feasible solutions to those in authority. The section also pointed out the fact

that the increasing rate of cybercrime Nigeria and other countries of the world is alarming and the one which need immediate attention. The section then further pin pointed the gaps in literature and how the study is to achieve them. The chapter then further discuss the research questions and objectives that will be used to guide the study and achieve the pin pointed gaps in literature. The significance and scope of the study was explicitly elucidated.

The second chapter of this study was able to cover two sections: the conceptual and the empirical review. The first section was able to give insight into the various academic definitions of cybercrime, the development and historical operations of cybercriminals over time, how globalization and the development of the internet, technological machines, and computer devices have aided in the growth of cybercrime, and finally, how cybercrime is perceived in the Nigerian context. The study examined various scholarly definitions of cybercrime from Nigeria as well as other parts of the world. The second section was able to also give insight into literatures on the nature and dynamics of cybercrime from a broader perspective on Nigerian society, certain factors that encourage youth involvement in cybercrime in Nigeria and around the world, and categories and types of cybercrime, the socioeconomic lifestyles of yahoo-boys, the impact of yahoo-yahoo on Nigerian society, and strategies aimed at reducing yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria. Finally, the chapter detailed the gaps in the literature that were filled as well as how those gaps were filled.

The third chapter entails the theoretical framework of the study, where sociological theories such as the differential association theory and the routine activity theory was employed. These theories served as a roadmap for the study by giving more explanations and insight to the study.

The fourth chapter contains the methodology employed in the study in achieving its aims and answering its questions. The study employed a convergent parallel research design, which is mostly used in a mixed method research tradition. The combination of the purposive sampling

technique and the accidental sampling technique was utilized in getting the sample size. A total of 273 respondents were employed, of which 230 respondents was employed to gather the quantitative data, while 13 respondents was employed to gather the qualitative data, across all faculties of the university. The study is a mixed method research that employed both questionnaire and interview in gather data from respondents. The study ensured all ethical considerations were met and the respondents gave their consents of participation.

The fifth chapter encompasses the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the field in alignment with the stated methods stipulated in the chapter 4 of the study, in other to ensure accuracy and proper guide the entire study. The findings from the study shows that undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University are aware of cybercrime and its implications on the society, also they believe cybercrime is rampant among undergraduate students of OAU. It further shows that factors such as peer pressure, financial issues, lack of job opportunities, influence from social media, lack of effective laws, and personal decisions are factors responsible for students' involvement in cybercrime. The study also shows that social media and its contents is a key influence for students' participation in cybercrime. In addition, the study proffers feasible solutions for minimizing cybercrime among students such as government introduction of stricter laws, education and awareness programs, introduction of cybersecurity course in school curriculum, and encouragement of students to report suspicious cybercrime activities.

6.2. Conclusion

In its final report, this study came to the conclusion students are aware of cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) and they know its implications and impact on the Nigerian society. They believe it has dented the image of Nigeria in the global, hence the need for a strict government response to the issue. The study also concluded that cybercriminal activities are not so rampant among Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students, following the quantitative data collected from participants, although majority of the respondents for the quantitative data collected believed that it is not so rampant, as students mainly focus on their academics. Additionally, it is easy to conclude that the perpetrators of cybercrime are mostly male because we are in a patriarchal society and the expectations on the male gender is higher. The age range of perpetrators can be seen as ranging between 15–40 years of age, in our contemporary society.

Furthermore, the study has been able to conclude that factors such as financial gains, lack of job opportunities, peer pressure, influence from social media posts of yahoo-boys, lack of effective cybercrime laws, and personal decisions are responsible for students' involvement in cybercrime. In addition to the above are factors such as: poor parenting, greed, poverty, family background, fear of the future, economic instability, societal acceptance, lack of satisfaction with their course of study, failed society, philosophy of education as scam, failure of government to crack down cybercriminals, and corruption of agencies put in place to curb cybercrime.

More so, the study has concluded that the consumption of social media content showcasing the lavish lifestyles of successful cybercriminals has significantly influenced students' involvement in cybercrime. Students are exposed to extravagant posts by cybercriminals on a daily basis, serving as a strong motivating factor for them to develop an interest and engage in such activities. Social

media platforms have also emerged as fertile grounds for cybercriminal activities, with numerous victims falling prey to scams initiated through these platforms. Additionally, social media serves as a meeting place where aspiring cybercriminals connect with experienced individuals, gaining mentorship and further motivation. While addressing the issue of flamboyant posts on social media may pose challenges, it is crucial for social media management to collaborate with the government in reducing such content without infringing upon the rights of users. Working together, they can implement measures to mitigate the glorification of cybercriminal activities while ensuring the platform remains a space for free expression and user engagement. By striking a balance, social media platforms can play a significant role in curbing the influence and attractiveness of cybercrime among students.

In conclusion, it is evident that the government's efforts in cracking down on cybercriminals are inadequate. This deficiency can be attributed to various factors, primarily the presence of corruption within the agencies responsible for investigating and apprehending these criminals. Instances have been reported where law enforcement personnel have been found accepting bribes from cybercriminals and subsequently releasing them back into society to continue their illicit activities. Therefore, the government is encouraged to do more in cracking down cybercriminals and ensure agencies are committed to the course of their establishment. Also, the study proffered other possible solutions such as; implementing stricter laws and punishment on cybercriminals, creating educational and awareness programmes, establishing anonymous reporting system, creating job opportunities, and providing scholarships and grants for students in order to make them focus on their studies and not think of cybercrime as an option to make money.

6.3: Contribution to the Body of Knowledge

This study has been able to broaden the body of knowledge by considering the way students, who are seen as the major perpetrator of cybercrime perceive it to be, the factors responsible for the increasing rate of cybercrime among students, the roles of social media and its content plays in influencing students' participation in cybercrime, and possible measures the government and university authorities can put in place in reducing this melee. The outcome of this study has drawn some distinctions compared to that of early scholars on cybercrime, factors responsible for it, the age range of perpetrators, and feasible solutions in minimizing it.

6.4: Limitations of the Study

This study has made a significant contribution to the body of knowledge on the topic of students' perception and the increasing rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students at Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU). However, there are limitations to this study, particularly regarding the collection of qualitative data from respondents. These limitations were primarily due to time and financial constraints.

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that future research on this topic continue to employ a mixed-methods approach to gather more comprehensive insights. By using both qualitative and quantitative methods, a more detailed understanding of the subject matter can be achieved. Additionally, it is suggested to conduct a comparative analysis between universities where "yahoo-yahoo" activities are prevalent and those where it is not. Exploring the reasons for this variation could provide valuable insights into the factors influencing cybercrime rates. Furthermore, it is advisable to increase the sample size, particularly for the collection of qualitative

data, in order to enhance the study's validity, and the overall findings and understanding of the subject matter.

6.5: Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations and feasible solutions are suggested to address the increasing rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students. The following practical suggestions can help minimize cybercrime incidents:

- i. **Integration Cybersecurity Course:** It is recommended that universities include a dedicated cybersecurity course in their curriculum. This course would educate students about the negative impacts of cybercrime on society and equip them with knowledge and skills to protect themselves from becoming victims;
- ii. **Implementation of Stricter Laws and Punishments:** Governments should enact stringent legislation to combat cybercrime and establish penalties that outweigh the potential benefits of engaging in such activities. These measures would serve as a strong deterrent for students and the wider population;
- iii. **Education and Awareness Programmes:** Promote education and awareness programs that explicitly convey the message that "yahoo-yahoo" or any form of illegal online activities is unacceptable and can have severe consequences. These programs should emphasize ethical ways of building wealth and the importance of responsible digital citizenship;
- iv. **Anonymous Reporting Platforms:** Establish anonymous reporting platforms where students can confidentially report cybercriminal activities they witness or encounter.

Additionally, governments can establish dedicated cybercrime response departments where students can physically report such incidents for prompt action;

- v. **Scholarships and Grants:** Governments, in collaboration with universities, should create more scholarships and grants, particularly for indigent students. These opportunities should be based on merit, providing incentives for students to focus on their studies and deter them from resorting to cybercrime;
- vi. **University Regulations:** University management should implement regulations, such as limiting the number of vehicles allowed on campus and requiring vehicle registration, to enhance security and control access. These measures can help prevent cybercriminal activities that may be facilitated through unauthorized vehicles;
- vii. **Job Opportunities Creation:** Universities should create more job opportunities for undergraduate students who are willing and capable of working while studying. Additionally, on a broader scale, the government should prioritize job creation for graduate students, ensuring they have access to meaningful employment with substantial pay.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

I am an undergraduate student from the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. I am conducting a study on “Students' Perception and Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduates”. Kindly note that there are no right or wrong answers, hence, your candid answer to each question is of great importance to the study and will help in devising effective measures in combating cybercrime and its prevalence among undergraduate students.

On this basis, I will like to seek your permission to be part of the participants whose opinion will help in achieving the aims and objectives of the study. Please note that, all information provided would be strictly used for academic purposes, hence, your utmost collaboration and cooperation will be well appreciated.

Please read the following set of questions carefully; then tick appropriately:

SECTION A: BIO-SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC DATA		
1.	Sex of Respondent	a. Male <input type="checkbox"/> b. Female <input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Age of Respondent	a. 16 – 25 <input type="checkbox"/> b. 26 – 35 <input type="checkbox"/> c. 36 – 45 <input type="checkbox"/> d. Above 46 <input type="checkbox"/>
3.	State of Origin	Specify:
4.	Religion	a. Christianity <input type="checkbox"/> b. Islam <input type="checkbox"/> c. Traditional Worship <input type="checkbox"/> d. Other:
5.	Level of Study	a. 100L <input type="checkbox"/> b. 200L <input type="checkbox"/> c. 300L <input type="checkbox"/> d. 400L <input type="checkbox"/> e. 500L <input type="checkbox"/> f. 600L <input type="checkbox"/>
6.	Faculty of Study	Specify:
7.	Course of Study	Specify:

SECTION B: UNDERSTANDING STUDENTS' PERCEPTION AS REGARDS CYBERCRIME (YAHOO-YAHOO)

8.	Are you aware of the phenomenon called cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) in Nigeria society?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
9.	Have you or anyone you know been a victim of cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo)?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
10.	Do you think cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) is a serious problem among students in Nigeria?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
11.	Do you think cybercriminal activities are rampant among OAU students?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
12.	Do you think cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) negatively affects the reputation of Nigeria?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
13.	Do you believe there are more male cybercrime perpetrators than that of female?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
14.	Do you feel exposure to the internet and social media influence the perception of cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) among university students?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION C: FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE INCREASING RATE OF STUDENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN CYBERCRIME

Note: SA - Strongly Agree | A - Agree | N - Neutral | D - Disagree | SD - Strongly Disagree

		SA	A	N	D	SD
15.	Students' involvement in cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) results from some financial reasons					
16.	Lack of job opportunities is a factor responsible for the increasing rate of cybercrime among students					
17.	The increasing rate of cybercrime among students is due to peer pressure					
18.	The increasing rate of cybercrime among students is due to the influence from social media posts of cybercriminals (yahoo-boys)					
19.	Lack of effective cybercrime laws is a factor responsible for the increasing rate of cybercrime among students					
20.	The rising prevalence of cybercrime among students can be attributed to the personal decision to participate in such action.					

SECTION D: EXAMINING HOW SOCIAL MEDIA CONTENTS OF CYBERCRIMINALS INFLUENCE STUDENTS' PARTICIPATION IN CYBERCRIME

21.	Which social media platforms do you use from the following options?	a. Facebook <input type="checkbox"/> b. Twitter <input type="checkbox"/> c. Instagram <input type="checkbox"/> d. Others:.....
22.	Have you ever come across any yahoo-boys flamboyant post while surfing the above social media platform?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
23.	Has the extravagant lifestyle o Yahoo boys prompted you to explore alternate means of earning income?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
24.	Do you believe that social media contents of cybercriminals can influence students' participation in cybercrime?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
25.	Do you think social media plays a role in promoting the activities of yahoo-yahoo in the cyberspace?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
26.	Have you ever fallen victim to cybercrime, or has anyone in your family?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
27.	If yes, do you think social media played a role in the victimization?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>
28.	Do you think social media platforms and government can work together to control the flaunting of wealth by Yahoo boys on social media?	a) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> b) No <input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION E: SUGGESTIONS OF MEASURES THAT CAN BE USED IN REDUCING CYBERCRIME AMONG UNIVERSITY UNDERGRADUATES

Note: SA - Strongly Agree | A - Agree | N - Neutral | D - Disagree | SD - Strongly Disagree

		SA	A	N	D	SD
29.	The government is doing enough to combat cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) in our society					
30.	Stricter laws and punishment for cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) will help reduce its occurrence among students					
31.	Education and awareness programs can help students understand the negative consequences of engaging in cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo)					
32.	You support the idea of creating a cybersecurity course as part of the university curriculum					
33.	You are more likely to report cybercrime activities if there was an anonymous reporting system in place?					

Thank you.

APPENDIX B: INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

Dear Respondent,

I am an undergraduate student of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, from the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences. I am conducting a study whose focus is to better understand “Students' Perception and Increasing Rate of Cybercrime Among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduates”. Your interest in participating in this study is well appreciated and not taken for granted. In addition, your genuine answers will help in developing effective measures in combating cybercrime and its dominance among undergraduate students. Your participation in this study is voluntary, and your responses are confidential. Please feel free to ask any questions at any point during the interview, as it would last for about 20minutes or less.

Kindly ensure that your responses are as honest as possible and devoid of any biases. Also, please note that there are no right or wrong answers, and your viewpoint and philosophy about the subject matter is of high importance. I would love to tape our conversions in order to reference back to it when necessary, and I assure the utmost confidentiality of our discussions.

Do I have your consent to proceed?

Socio-demographic data of participants

1. Recommended Pseudo name:
2. Age:
3. Gender:
4. State of Origin:
5. Level of study:
6. Course of Study:
7. Faculty of study:

What is students' perception of cybercrime?

- i. What do you understand by the term "cybercrime" or "yahoo-yahoo"?
- ii. In your opinion, do you think yahoo-yahoo poses any kind of threat on the Nigeria society?
- iii. Can you give examples of cybercrime that you are aware of?
- iv. Have you or anyone related to you been a victim of cybercrime? If so, how did it happen?
- v. In your opinion, what category of people do you think are more involved in cybercrime?

What are the factors responsible for the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime?

- i. In your opinion, do you think cybercrime is predominant among undergraduates, specifically, Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students? How.
- ii. What are some factors you believe might influence the increasing rate of students' involvement in cybercrime?

How do social media (such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) contents of cybercriminals influence students' participation in cybercrime?

- i. Do you think social media platforms (like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram) have contributed to the increasing rate of cybercrime and cybercriminal activities among students and how?
- ii. Considering the flamboyant display of wealth of yahoo-boys on various social medium, in what ways do you think it can influence the involvement of students into yahoo-yahoo?
- iii. In your opinion, how do you think the government or social media platforms can regulate the flamboyant display of wealth by yahoo-boys on social media?

What are the feasible solutions for minimizing the increasing rate of cybercrime among undergraduate students?

- i. Do you think the increasing rate of yahoo-yahoo have any impact on the way Nigerians are being viewed globally?
- ii. How do you think the university authorities can better address cybercrime among undergraduate students?
- iii. On a broader scale, what measures do you think the government can put in place in minimizing the rate of cybercrime among students?